

1 **QUALITY AROMA IMPROVEMENT OF MUSCAT WINE SPIRITS: A NEW**
2 **APPROACH USING FIRST-PRINCIPLES MODEL-BASED DESIGN AND MULTI-**
3 **OBJECTIVE DYNAMIC OPTIMIZATION THROUGH MULTI-VARIABLE**
4 **ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES**

5
6 Ricardo Luna ^a, Pau Matias-Guiu ^b, Francisco López ^b, José R. Pérez-Correa ^{a,c *}.

7 ^a Departamento de Ingeniería Química y Bioprocesos, Pontificia Universidad Católica de
8 Chile, Vicuña Mackenna 4860, Casilla 306, Santiago 22, Chile, rlluna@uc.cl

9 ^b Departament d'Enginyeria Química, Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Av. Països Catalans 26,
10 43007, Tarragona, Spain, pau.matiasguiu@urv.cat, francisco.lopez@urv.cat

11 ^c Departamento de Automação e Sistemas, Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Centro
12 Tecnológico, Bairro Trindade, Caixa Postal 476, Florianópolis-SC, 88040-900, Brazil.

13

14 *Corresponding author José R. Pérez-Correa: perez@ing.puc.cl; phone: [+562-23544258](tel:+562-23544258)*

15

16

17

18

19

20

21

22

23 **ABSTRACT**

24

25 This work proposes a model-based methodology to produce recipes for Muscat wine
26 distillations in Charentais alembics. The recipes were obtained by dynamic multi-objective
27 optimization of a multi-component first-principles model. Two multi-objective functions
28 were developed considering chemical markers that define the aromatic characteristic of the
29 distillates. The first function included three chemical markers characteristic of each
30 distillation cut (head, heart and tail). The second considered a Principal Component analysis
31 (PCA) applied to the chemical profile of Chilean commercial distillates. The optimal recipes
32 were experimentally validated in an automatized Charentais alembic using a synthetic
33 Muscat wine consisting of ethanol, water plus six congeners. The experimental results
34 indicated that using model-based optimization techniques, it is possible to obtain spirits with
35 a chemical composition like some Chilean commercial distillates. In addition, the chemical
36 composition of many commercial distillates located close to a Pareto front defining a
37 compromise between linalool, a characteristic Muscat floral aroma, and acetaldehyde, a head
38 contaminant marker.

39

40 **Keywords:** Dynamic multi- objective optimization; Principal component analysis (PCA);
41 Mass and energy balances; Muscat wine spirits; Distillation strategies; Linalool.

42

43

44 1 INTRODUCTION

45

46 Distilled spirits, normally produced from the surplus of cereals and fruits available in a given
47 region, are characterized by a distinctive aroma. Barley is used in both Scotch Whisky and
48 Irish Whiskey. Barley, corn and rye are used to produce bourbon in USA. Cane juice is used
49 to produce rum in the Caribbean and cachaça in Brazil, while agave is used to produce tequila
50 in Mexico. Grapes are used to produce several kinds of distillates, like brandy in Spain,
51 cognac in France, as well as pisco in Chile and Peru (Small et al., 2011). These beverages
52 are mainly composed of water and ethanol, representing 97-99 % of the total content of the
53 spirits. However, the distinctive aroma and quality of these spirits is defined by hundreds of
54 low concentration compounds called congeners. These compounds explain the difference in
55 flavor and aroma between 2 spirits, such as whisky and pisco. The concentration of these
56 congeners depends on many variables such as growing conditions, fermentation variables,
57 yeast strain, distillation equipment, distillation variables, as well as maturation and aging
58 conditions. Distillation plays a key role in preserving the distinctive aroma of young spirits
59 (López et al., 2017).

60 Traditional systems, like copper Charentais alembics (French style) and batch distillation
61 tray-columns (German style), are normally used to produce young spirits like pisco and
62 cachaça. Charentais alembics are widely used in small scale facilities since their operation is
63 much simpler than batch columns and are more suitable to preserve the original fruit aroma
64 (Arrieta-Garay et al., 2013). It has been observed that batch distillations with packed-columns
65 allow fast and flexible control of the internal reflux rate (Matias-Guiu et al., 2018, 2016;
66 Rodríguez-Bencomo et al., 2016), although the process is much less reproducible than

67 distillations with Charentais alembics (García-Llobodanin et al., 2011). Nonetheless,
68 alembics are subjected to many uncontrolled and unmeasured disturbances that also generate
69 variability in the composition of the final product (Luna et al., 2018). In these systems, three
70 cuts are collected sequentially: head, heart and tail. There are different criteria to define the
71 cuts during the distillation, such as ethanol recovery, alcoholic strength (Spaho et al., 2013)
72 or the temperature of the vapor before it enters the condenser (Spaho, 2017). Distillers, based
73 on experience and on-line tasting and smelling, define the cut-times to balance the congeners
74 to attain spirits with good aroma and no off-flavors. This remains the most reliable method
75 to determine cut-times. In the last decades, spirits distillation mathematical models have been
76 developed for better understanding the behavior of volatile aroma compounds (Puentes et al.,
77 2018). Volatile aroma compounds such as terpenes and esters (floral and fruity aroma) are
78 considered positive quality factors and other compounds such as acetaldehyde and fatty acids
79 (off-flavors), and toxic compounds (such as methanol) are considered negative impact
80 aromas and deleterious to spirits quality (Tsakiris et al., 2014). Therefore, spirits quality and
81 safety are related to the handling and control of some volatile aroma compounds in the
82 distillate. In spirits distillation, first principle models include mass and energy balances, a
83 hydraulic model, and several relationships describing physical properties and thermodynamic
84 equilibrium. For dynamic operation and batch distillations, these models are described by a
85 set of differential and algebraic equations (DAEs). Several spirits distillation first-principles
86 models have been developed for batch distillation, for example, pisco distillation in plate
87 columns (Osorio et al., 2004), pisco distillation in packed columns (Carvallo et al., 2011),
88 cachaça distillation (Scanavini et al., 2012, 2010) in copper alembic and pear distillation in
89 copper Charentais alembic (Sacher et al., 2013). Additionally, commercial process simulators
90 have been used to simulate spirits batch distillation in pot stills, for example, fruit spirits

91 distillation (Claus and Berglund, 2009), whisky distillation (Valderrama et al., 2012) and
92 bitter orange distillation (Esteban-Decloux et al., 2014). However, most of these studies
93 constrained the operating conditions in their simulations to replicate experimental
94 distillations to predict the aroma composition in the distillate. Normally, new operating
95 conditions are rarely explored via simulations to obtain distillates with different aroma
96 profile. Nevertheless, some authors have applied optimization techniques in model-based
97 decision making to explore the impact of new operating conditions. For instance, these
98 techniques have been used to define optimal operating variables, such as distillation cut-
99 times, reflux rate path in batch distillation columns (De Lucca et al., 2013; Osorio et al.,
100 2005) and heating power path in an alembic boiler (Luna et al., 2018).

101 Model based design has many advantages, such as being much faster and cheaper than
102 experimental trial and error. Dynamic optimization techniques, using the sequential or the
103 simultaneous approach (Srinivasan et al., 2003), can be applied to design optimal operating
104 strategies for batch distillations. In the sequential method, the model equations and the
105 objective function are calculated in successive evaluations, i.e., the DAEs are solved
106 independently of the objective function (Safdarnejad et al., 2015). In this case, only the
107 manipulated variable is discretized as a piecewise polynomial and the decision variables of
108 the optimization problem are the polynomial coefficients (Barton et al., 1998; Vassiliadis et
109 al., 1994a, 1994b). In the simultaneous approach, the model equations and the optimization
110 problem are solved together (Hedengren et al., 2014). In this formulation, manipulated
111 variables and state variables are both discretized; differential equations are transformed into
112 algebraic equations, for example using orthogonal collocation on finite elements
113 (Kameswaran and Biegler, 2006). For problems with a moderate number of state variables,

114 the simultaneous approach is faster and can handle more decision variables and constraints
115 than the sequential approach (Hedengren et al., 2014). However, for problems with a small
116 number of decision variables and a large-scale model with many state variables, sequential
117 methods perform better.

118 Dynamic optimization problems in batch distillation usually consider goals, such as minimize
119 process time, maximize the amount of distillate or of a key component, and maximize
120 economic profit (Diwekar, 1995; Mujtaba, 2004). In batch distillation of alcoholic beverages,
121 dynamic optimization problems have been formulated through multi-objective functions
122 since there are some objectives that should be minimized (off-flavors and toxic compounds)
123 and others that should be maximized (terpenes and fruity esters). Osorio et al. (2005) used a
124 multi-objective dynamic optimization weighting method to maximize ethanol and linalool
125 recoveries and minimize the octanoic acid recovery of wine spirits in a tray column. Luna et
126 al. (2018) used a weighting method in the dynamic optimization of an alembic distillation to
127 maximize the ethanol recovery and minimize the methanol concentration. Matias-Guiu et al.
128 (2018) applied a multi-objective optimization based on the desirability approach, using a
129 response surface model to improve the aroma of a Muscat spirit distilled in a batch packed
130 column. In the desirability approach, the conflicting objectives are transformed into a range
131 of acceptability values between 0 and 1, ranging from an undesirable to a desirable objective,
132 respectively. When the number of objectives is high, solving the multi-objective problem is
133 difficult, since many conflicting objectives appear that complicate the visualization and
134 interpretation of the solution space, hampering the decision-making process (Pozo et al.,
135 2012). An alternative approach is to use dimension reduction methods that allow for omitting
136 redundant metrics from the problem to keep it at a manageable size.

137 In this study, we used Principal component analysis (PCA) to reduce the dimensionality of a
138 multi-objective dynamic distillation optimization problem. We focused on a model-based
139 design and assessed experimentally the optimal distillation strategies for young Muscat
140 spirits in a Charentais alembic. The aim was to obtain a distillate rich in fruit and floral
141 aromas and low in off-flavors and toxic compounds. A first-principles dynamic model of a
142 Charentais alembic (Luna et al., 2018) was extended to include six congeners representing
143 reliable markers of each distillate cut. In addition, principal component analysis (PCA) was
144 applied to analyze Chilean commercial piscos. Two dynamic optimization problems with two
145 objectives each were formulated and solved using the sequential approach. To reduce the
146 problem's dimensionality, the objectives were a weighting function based on chemical
147 markers and a weighting function based on PCA decomposition. Experimental computer-
148 controlled distillations were carried out to calibrate the model and to compare standard
149 distillation strategies with optimum operation. The decision variables were the heating power
150 path, the head volume cut, and the heart volume cut.

151

152 **2 MATERIALS AND METHODS**

153 **2.1 Distillation system**

154

155 The Charentais copper alembic with automatic control used in our experiments consists of a
156 4.8 L capacity boiler, a natural convection partial condenser (head), a swan neck and a total
157 condenser. PT100 sensors measured the boiler, head and room temperatures. The heating
158 power (750 W) applied to the boiler was manipulated using an RG solid state controller
159 (Carlo Gavazzi, RGC1P series, Italy). A Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) (S7-1200

160 Siemens, Germany) received the temperature data from the PT100 sensors and sent the
161 controller output to the RG solid state. A human-machine interface (HMI) and an internal
162 model control (IMC) algorithm were coded in MATLAB[®]/Simulink[™] using the TCP/IP
163 communication protocol with TIA Portal V14 SP1 in a PC (Intel[®] Core[™] i5 7th Gen Hewlett-
164 Packard ProDesk 400MT, USA). In the main control loop, the measured variable was the
165 alembic's head temperature and the manipulating variable was the heating power in the
166 alembic's boiler.

167 **2.2 Synthetic Muscat wine and experiments**

168 *Wines*

169 Model calibration and validation were carried out using data from distillations with a
170 synthetic wine consisting of a mixture of water-ethanol (11.4 % of alcoholic strength, pH
171 3.2) and six congeners that were adjusted to obtain a composition similar to a Muscat wine
172 (2016 vintage year) (Matias-Guiu et al., 2018). This mixture was prepared once, with enough
173 for all the experimental distillations. In each distillation run, the alembic was initially loaded
174 with 1.8 kg of synthetic wine, equivalent to 95 moles (M_0) and 0.038 ethanol molar fraction
175 (x_0). Table 1 shows the congener composition of both the synthetic and Muscat wines.

176 *Model fitting experiments*

177 Two distillation strategies were performed in triplicate, applying different heating powers in
178 the boiler: (i) slow distillation at constant low heating power (250W) and (ii) fast distillation
179 at constant high heating power (450 W). In all distillation runs, three fractions were collected
180 according to predefined volumes: 85 mL of head (sub-fractions 1-2), 375 mL of heart (sub-
181 fractions 3-11) and 115 mL of tail (sub-fractions 12-15). The total amount collected was 640

182 mL. The corresponding total distillation times were 170 and 68 min for the slow and fast
183 distillations respectively.

184 *Optimization experiments*

185 Two optimal strategies, obtained by multi-objective dynamic optimization, were carried out
186 in triplicate. The first strategy, called w13, was obtained by a weighting function based on
187 chemical markers (MO1) (see section 2.9.1). The second strategy, called PCh6, was obtained
188 by a weighting function based on PCA decomposition (MO2) (see section 2.9.2). Optimal
189 distillation runs finished when the heart fraction was collected. The head and heart fractions
190 were collected according to the corresponding multi-objective dynamic optimization
191 strategy. For w13, the head and heart fractions were 81.6 and 245.4 mL respectively (see
192 section 3.3). For PCh6, the head and heart fractions were 157.3 and 460.1 mL respectively
193 (see section 3.4).

194 **2.3 Chemical analysis**

195 The ethanol content of wine and distillation residues were determined by ebulliometry
196 (electronic ebulliometer, GAB instruments, Moja-Olèrdola, Spain), wine pH was measured
197 with a pH-meter (Crison Basic 20, L'Hospitalet de Llobregat, Spain) and ethanol content of
198 distilled samples was measured with an electronic density meter (Anton Paar DSA 5000M,
199 Graz, Austria).

200 Volatile compounds of wines and distillation residues were extracted in duplicate with
201 dichloromethane for further chromatographic analysis, using a methodology adapted from
202 Ferreira et al. (1998). Thus, 10 mL of wine were added to a 12-mL glass tube with 50 μ L of
203 the internal standard solution (400 mg/L of 2-octanol, Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, USA),

204 2.5 g of ammonium sulfate (PanReac Química, S.A.U. Castellar del Vallès, Spain) and 0.5
205 mL of dichloromethane (PanReac Química, S.A.U. Castellar del Vallès, Spain). Liquid-
206 liquid extractions were carried out for 1 h in an orbital shaker at 110 rpm.

207 To perform the analysis of distilled samples, 50 μ L of the internal standard solution (400
208 mg/L of 2-octanol, Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, USA) were added to 1 mL of distilled sample
209 (previously adjusted to an alcoholic strength by volume of 40 % v/v to avoid matrix effects
210 during chromatographic analysis). All analyses were performed 21 days after each
211 distillation.

212 **2.4 Chromatographic analysis**

213 Chromatographic analyses were performed using a gas chromatograph equipped with a flame
214 ionization detector (GC-FID) (Agilent 6890, Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany),
215 an autosampler (Agilent 7683, Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) and a capillary
216 polar column (MetaWAX, 60 m length, 0.25 mm ID and 0.5 μ m phase thickness) from
217 Teknokroma (Barcelona, Spain). Injection (2 μ L) was done in split mode (1:5). Injector and
218 detector temperatures were 250 °C and 260 °C, respectively. Oven temperature program was:
219 40 °C (5 min), 7 °C/min up to 100 °C (15 min), 3 °C/min up to 140 °C and 2 °C/min up to
220 200 °C (16 min). Column-head flow was initially set at 0.5 mL/min (28 min) and increased
221 with a rate of 5 mL/min² up to 1.1 mL/min using helium as carrier gas. Quantifications were
222 carried out by interpolation of calibration curves built with a synthetic hydro-alcoholic
223 solution (40% v/v of ethanol) spiked with the selected compounds at different levels.
224 Reagents' CAS, supplier companies, purity and Kovats retention indices are shown in Table
225 S1. Detection and quantification limits were determined by signal-to-noise ratios (S/N) of 3
226 and 10, respectively.

227 2.5 Principal component analysis

228 Principal component analysis (PCA) (Jolliffe, 2002) was performed with nine Chilean
229 commercial piscos (number of observations) and six congeners (number of variables)
230 selected for the phenomenological model in section 2.6. The Chilean piscos were analyzed
231 using GC-FID (see section 2.4). Table S2 shows the congener concentrations of the
232 commercial piscos. Each variable was standardized according to the maximum concentration
233 observed, and then normalized considering that the measured data follows a normal
234 distribution,

$$Z = \frac{X - \mu}{\sigma} \quad (1)$$

235

236 where X corresponds to the PCA standardized variables, μ is the mean of the sample of the
237 respective variable and σ is the corresponding standard deviation. The PCA method was
238 coded in MATLAB® R2015a using the *statistics toolbox*. Figure S1 shows the PCA results,
239 where the congeners were distributed in three quadrants; (i) acetaldehyde and hexanoic acid,
240 (ii) ethyl acetate, methanol and β -phenylethanol, and (iii) linalool.

241 2.6 Modeling

242 The original ternary model of the alembic, developed by Luna et al. (2018), was expanded to
243 include five new congeners characteristic of the different distillation cuts:

244 i) *Head cut*: acetaldehyde and ethyl acetate provide negative impact aromas in the final
245 product; to reduce the content of these compounds in the heart cut, they should be recovered
246 as much as possible in the head cut (Christoph and Bauer-Christoph, 2007).

247 ii) *Heart cut*: linalool is a terpenic compound characteristic of young Muscat wine distillates;
248 it provides a desirable flowery note (Christoph and Bauer-Christoph, 2007).

249 iii) *Tail cut*: hexanoic acid provides a rancid aroma and is considered a defect in young spirits;
250 although it provides a positive rose aroma, β -phenylethanol is a an odor marker of tail
251 compounds (Christoph and Bauer-Christoph, 2007).

252 In addition, PCA equations of these congeners in Chilean commercial piscos were added to
253 the DAE system (see section 2.5). Then, the two principal components where compared
254 between the congener simulations from the heart cut and the commercial Chilean pisco's
255 data.

256 2.7 Model calibration

257 The data obtained in the constant heat rate distillations with synthetic wine (see Section 2.2)
258 were used to calibrate the dynamic alembic model. The fitting parameters were:

$$\theta = [UA_b, UA_c, M_0, x_0, x_{0,cong}] \quad (2)$$

259

260 Where UA_b and UA_c represent the global heat transfer coefficient multiplied by the
261 corresponding heat transfer area in the boiler and head, respectively. M_0 , x_0 and $x_{0,cong}$ are
262 the initial total moles, ethanol molar fraction and congeners molar fraction in the boiler just
263 when the first drop of distillate is recovered. The calibration cost function was:

$$J(\theta) = \sum_j^{n_{var}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{obs}} \left(\frac{\hat{y}_{ij}(u, \theta, t) - y_{ij}(u, t)}{\max(y_{ij})} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

264

265 where index j represents the measured variables and index i the samples times. The measured
 266 variables were: distilled volume V , head temperature T_c , alcoholic strength GA and relative
 267 congener concentration ($N_{cong} = 1 \dots 6$). $\max(y_{ij})$ corresponds to the maximum measured
 268 value of variable j during the distillation run. The optimization problem was solved within
 269 MATLAB® R2015a with a scatter search metaheuristic code (SSM) (Egea et al., 2007).

270 The average concentration of the distillate stream leaving the system at the corresponding
 271 time interval where the sample was collected is given by:

$$GA_i = \frac{\Delta GA}{\Delta V} = \left(\frac{M_D^g(t_{exp,i}) - M_D^g(t_{exp,i-1})}{V(t_{exp,i}) - V(t_{exp,i-1})} \right) \cdot PM_E \cdot \frac{1}{\rho_e} \cdot 100 \quad (4)$$

272

$$C_{cong,i} = \frac{\Delta C_{cong}}{\Delta V} = \left(\frac{M_{D,cong}(t_{exp,i}) - M_{D,cong}(t_{exp,i-1})}{(V(t_{exp,i}) - V(t_{exp,i-1})) \cdot (GA_i/100)} \right) \cdot MW_{cong} \cdot 1000 \quad (5)$$

273

274 where GA_i and $C_{cong,i}$ are the average alcoholic strength and average relative congener
 275 concentration in each collected sample, respectively.

276 **2.8 Random simulation design**

277 To explore the scope of the model, several simulations were carried out varying input
 278 variables (heat input and cut volumes) with uniformly distributed random values.
 279 Specifically, we searched for operating conditions that yield distillates (in the PCA map) like
 280 Chilean commercial piscos. Three cases were assessed: (i) random heating power path and
 281 fixed head and heart cuts, (ii) fixed heating power path and random head and heart cuts, (iii)
 282 random heating power path and random head and heart cuts. The heating power path was

283 discretized in 19 time steps in both the head cut and heart cut. In each case, one hundred
284 simulations were carried out; the heating power path values varied between 250 and 450 W,
285 UA_b and UA_c parameters were assumed a linear function between the heating power (250W
286 and 450W) and their estimated values (see section 3.1), the head volume varied between 75
287 and 230 mL, and the heart volume varied between 270 and 630 mL. Simulated congener
288 composition in the heart cut (model output) defined the two principal components and these
289 were compared with the commercial distillates in the PCA map.

290 **2.9 Multi-objective dynamic optimization**

291 In chemical engineering, multi-objective optimization problems are commonly encountered
292 when several conflicting objectives should be simultaneously satisfied (Bonilla-Petriciolet
293 and Rangaiah, 2013; Sharma and Rangaiah, 2013). Thus, a set of several optimal solutions
294 can be obtained; this is called the Pareto set (Bhaskar et al., 2000). Even though there are
295 many efficient methods to obtain the Pareto set, in our work we used the simple weighting
296 method (Miettinen and Hakanen, 2009). We defined two cost functions: one based on three
297 chemical markers (one for each distillation cut) and another based on PCA decomposition.

298 **2.9.1 Multi-objective weighting function based on chemical markers**

299 A multi-objective cost function was defined to get a heart composition that compromises
300 conflicting criteria, i.e., low head compounds, high heart compounds and low tail
301 compounds. Three chemical markers define the distillation cuts: acetaldehyde for head cut,
302 linalool for heart cut and β -phenylethanol for tail cut. Hence, the multi-objective cost
303 function was specified in terms of these chemical markers, i.e., minimize acetaldehyde,
304 maximize linalool and minimize β -phenylethanol:

$$Min J_1 = \alpha \cdot \frac{C_{acet}(t_f)}{150} - \beta \frac{C_{lin}(t_f)}{2} + \gamma \frac{C_{\beta-feOH}(t_f)}{20} \quad (6)$$

$$305 \quad \alpha + \beta + \gamma = 1$$

$$306 \quad 0 < \alpha < 1$$

$$307 \quad 0 < \beta < 1$$

$$308 \quad 0 < \gamma < 1$$

309 where, α (defined positive, to minimize acetaldehyde), $-\beta$ (defined negative, to maximize
 310 linalool) and γ (defined positive, to minimize β -phenylethanol) are the relative weights of
 311 each objective. C_{acet} , C_{lin} and $C_{\beta-feOH}$ are the relative congener concentration in g/hL.a.a.
 312 for acetaldehyde, linalool and β -phenylethanol respectively. All objectives were scaled by
 313 their maximum values: acetaldehyde maximum concentration in spirits allowed by the
 314 Chilean law (Biblioteca del congreso nacional de Chile and Ministerio de Agricultura, 2012),
 315 linalool maximum concentration observed by Matias-Guiu et al. (2018) in Muscat wine
 316 distillations and β -phenylethanol maximum concentration observed by Bordiga et al. (2013)
 317 in Muscat wines. Six levels for each weight were defined ($\alpha, \beta, \gamma = [0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1]$);
 318 all combinations where the sum of the weights was one were tried, resulting in 21
 319 optimization problems (see Table 3). Each of them was run at least twice to ensure we find
 320 the global minimum.

321 **2.9.2 Multi-objective weighting function based on PCA decomposition**

322 In this case, the aim was to reproduce the chemical profile of different Chilean commercial
 323 piscos, using two principal components; hence,

$$Min J_2 = (PCA_1 - PCA_{1,target})^2 + (PCA_2 - PCA_{2,target})^2 \quad (7)$$

324

325 where PCA_1 and PCA_2 are the principal components of the chemical profiles obtained from
326 the simulation of the distillation. $PCA_{1,target}$ and $PCA_{2,target}$ are the principal components
327 of the chemical profile of the target piscos. Five targets (Chilean commercial piscos) were
328 arbitrarily defined: PCh3, PCh4, PCh5, PCh6 and PCh8. According to the exploratory
329 simulations, some of them were within the reachable space of the simulated distillation
330 system and others were unreachable.

331 **2.9.3 Multi-objective dynamic optimization formulation**

332 The optimization variables were the heating power, the volume of the head cut and the
333 volume of the heart cut. Additional optimization constraints were: (i) heating power varied
334 between 250 and 450 W, (ii) volume head cut between 40 and 150 mL, (iii) volume heart cut
335 between 200 and 500 mL and finally, (iv) ethanol recovery in the heart cut must be higher
336 than 35%. Like random exploratory simulations (see section 2.8), UA_b and UA_c parameters
337 were assumed a linear function of the heating power.

338 The numerical method applied to solve the optimization problem was the sequential solution
339 (Srinivasan et al., 2003). The heat input was discretized into equally spaced time intervals:

$$u(\Delta t_i) = a_i \quad (8)$$

340

341 where index i represents the n-th time intervals and a_i represents the value of the heat input
342 u in the i-th time interval. Random exploratory simulations were carried out discretizing the
343 heating power path in 19, 9 and 4 time steps in the head and heart cuts. Figure S2 indicates
344 that the number of time steps size does not have a significant impact in the aromatic

345 composition of the head cut. In each simulation case, the results showed similar dispersion
346 and location in the PCA map. Therefore, the head cut was discretized into three time steps,
347 while the heart cut was discretized into six time steps. The optimization problem was solved
348 within MATLAB[®] R2015a with a scatter search metaheuristic code (SSM) and the dynamic
349 model of the alembic was solved with MATLAB's solver *ode15s*. The simultaneous
350 approach was not applied since we experienced convergence difficulties with our
351 optimization problem.

352 **3 RESULTS**

353 **3.1 Model calibration**

354 Figures S3 and S4 show measured values and model outputs of ethanol content, head
355 temperature, distillate volume and congener composition in the distillate of the three
356 replicates of the fast heating rate distillation (450 W). In turn, Figures S5 and S6 show the
357 fitted variables for the slow heating rate distillation (250 W). The 95% confidence intervals
358 shown in the figures were obtained by simulation, considering the standard deviation in the
359 estimated parameters set ($\theta \pm 2\sigma_\theta$). Table 2 shows the fitted parameters for the slow and fast
360 heating power.

361 Both distillation strategies (250 W and 450 W) yielded similar shapes of the evolution curves
362 over time for all compounds. Initial and final values were similar for ethanol, acetaldehyde,
363 ethyl acetate and linalool. Distillations at 450 W evolved faster and were completed in a bit
364 more than 60 minutes. Distillations at 250 W evolved slower and were completed in 160 min.
365 In line with what was observed by Matias-Guiu et al. (2018), our experiments and simulations
366 showed higher concentrations of tail compounds in the longer distillations (250 W strategy);
367 300 vs 180 g/hLa.a. of methanol, 85 vs 25 g/hLa.a. of hexanoic acid and 400 vs 140 g/hLa.a.

368 of β -phenylethanol. Model fitting was in most cases better for the high heating rate
369 distillation than for the low heating rate distillation. Luna et al. (2018) had reported similar
370 behavior with the same system but with a simpler mixture, arguing that the higher process
371 time required by the slow distillation made measurements more prone to disturbances. The
372 alcoholic strength and the distilled volume were the best fitted variables in both distillation
373 strategies, as observed by Luna et al. (2018).

374 Head compounds like acetaldehyde and ethyl acetate were predicted well in the head and
375 heart fraction, but in the tail fraction the predictions worsened. Model predictions of
376 acetaldehyde and ethyl acetate were zero in the tail fraction, while measurements showed
377 increasing values. By the end of the distillation, acetaldehyde and ethyl acetate
378 concentrations showed a slower decline than ethanol. Therefore, its relative concentrations
379 are extremely sensitive to ethanol and their measured values in the tail fraction increased.
380 The heart compound linalool was predicted well in all cuts (head, heart and tail) in both fast
381 and slow heating rate distillations. Methanol was predicted well in both strategies in all cuts,
382 especially in the tail cut. Moreover, its predictions were even better than those observed by
383 Luna et al. (2018), since in this work we used a better analytical method. Model predictions
384 of hexanoic acid during the heart cut were below the experimental values in both distillations.
385 Finally, in both strategies and all cuts, β -phenylethanol measurements were within the
386 confidence interval of the model predictions.

387 Congeners such as acetaldehyde, ethyl acetate and methanol were simulated and validated
388 for Charentais alembic distillations of pear wine in Sacher et al. (2013) and Sacher et al.
389 (2017). These compounds were predicted well and showed the same trend observed in our
390 results. However, β -phenylethanol was not predicted well in their simulations. According to

391 the simulations of Sacher et al. (2017), this compound distilled mainly in the heart fraction,
392 while in our simulations β -phenylethanol distilled mainly in the tail cut. Sacher et al. (2013)
393 distilled a pear distillate with 17.9% v/v of ethanol obtained from a previous distillation,
394 whereas our experiments distilled a synthetic wine with 11.4% v/v of ethanol. In addition,
395 initial concentrations of β -phenylethanol in our experiments were 5 times higher than in
396 Sacher et al. (2013).

397 Table 2 shows that for both strategies the estimated heat transfer parameter of the boiler was
398 practically the same. The heat transfer parameter of the boiler was less dependent on the
399 heating power in our case, since the heating element is inside the boiler (Luna et al. 2018).
400 In turn, the heat transfer parameter of the head increased with the heating power and was
401 higher than the heat transfer parameter of the boiler. This behavior was also observed by
402 Luna et al. (2018) and Sacher et al. (2013), arguing that high heating powers induce higher
403 convective air streams, increasing the heat transfer in the head.

404 **3.2 Random exploratory conditions**

405 Figure 1 shows the results obtained for three simulation cases: (i) random heating power path
406 and fixed cuts, (ii) fixed heating power path and random cuts, (iii) random heating power
407 path and random cuts. The distillation recipes with different heating rates (distillation rates)
408 and constant volume cuts yielded distillates that were concentrated in a relatively small
409 region in the PCA map (symbol \times in Figure 1). Instead, distillation recipes with different
410 volume cuts and constant heating rates reached a wider region in the PCA map (symbol $+$
411 in Figure 1). These results indicate that cut volumes have a higher influence on the aromatic
412 composition of the distillate (PCA map) than distillation heating rates. When heating power
413 and volume cuts were both varied, the reachable space was even wider (symbol \blacktriangle in Figure

414 1), and yielding distillates close to commercial distillates such as PCh3, PCh5, PCh6 and
415 PCh8, even though these commercial piscos are obtained in plate column stills in Chile.

416 The model could not reproduce some distillates like PCh1, PCh2, PCh4, PCh7 and PCh9.
417 This zone in the PCA map, which is rich in linalool and poor in acetaldehyde, is unreachable
418 with our simulations since:

419 i) The initial concentration of linalool of our synthetic wine is lower than that of some Muscat
420 wines.

421 ii) Our model did not consider chemical reactions, in particular the hydrolysis of bounded
422 aromas that occurred during the distillation of Muscat wines (Agosin et al., 2000).

423 iii) Commercial distillates were produced using plate column stills with higher rectification
424 capacity than Charentais alembics.

425 iv) Some of these commercial distillates were obtained by double or triple distillation and
426 our simulations considered a single distillation.

427 **3.3 Multi-objective weighting function based on chemical markers (MO1) and** 428 **experimental validation**

429 Table 3 shows the MO1 optimization results for all weight combinations, including head and
430 heart volumes, ethanol recovery in the heart cut, relative concentrations (g/hLa.a.) of
431 acetaldehyde, linalool and β -phenylethanol as well as PCA_1 and PCA_2 coordinates. During
432 the distillation process, acetaldehyde and linalool are highly volatile and appear in the first
433 fractions of the distillate. Nevertheless, acetaldehyde should be distilled as much as possible
434 in the head cut and linalool should not be lost in the head cut but instead recovered in the
435 heart cut. Our results in Table 3 indicate that acetaldehyde concentration (0.70 g/hLa.a.) is

436 minimized when α take on the highest value (run w1); the head and heart cuts were the largest
437 (248.7 and 483.6 mL respectively). Other objectives took on undesirable values; ethanol
438 recovery in the heart fraction (35.2%) was the smallest, linalool concentration was minimum
439 (0.061 g/hL.a.a.) and β -phenylethanol concentration was maximum (43.92 g/hLa.a.).
440 Maximum linalool concentrations (0.930 g/hL.a.a.) were obtained for $\alpha = 0$. In these cases,
441 the head and heart volume cuts were the smallest (205.4 and 46.8 mL respectively), ethanol
442 recovery in the heart fraction was the largest (54.7%), acetaldehyde was maximized (91.46
443 g/hLa.a.) and β -phenylethanol was minimized (9.12 g/hLa.a.). Hence, maximum linalool
444 concentrations in the heart coincide with maximum acetaldehyde concentrations, evidencing
445 a clear trade off that must be solved. In turn, β -phenylethanol is less volatile and appears
446 mainly in the last fraction of the distillate (Figure S4 and S6) and should not be distilled in
447 the heart fraction. Consequently, to minimize β -phenylethanol in the heart, the head and heart
448 cuts should be the shortest. Linalool and β -phenylethanol are harmonic objectives, i.e.,
449 achieving an improvement in one objective will also lead to an improvement in the other
450 (Weise, 2008). Thus, it is convenient to define the multi-objective cost function with only
451 two objectives (chemical markers): acetaldehyde and linalool or acetaldehyde and β -
452 phenylethanol, i.e., the head marker with the heart marker or the head marker with the tail
453 marker (see Table S3).

454 Matias-Guiu et al. (2018) reported the same behavior in a packed column still. Large head
455 volumes favored the extraction of ethanol, head compounds (like acetaldehyde) and linalool
456 in the head-cut, consequently reducing their levels in the heart-cut, while increased tail
457 compounds (like β -phenylethanol) in the heart-cut. They also observed that large heart
458 volumes favored high levels of tail compounds in the heart-cut.

459 The w13 optimal simulation was chosen to validate the alembic model. Figure S7 shows the
460 tracking of the optimal set-point in the head temperature, the evolution of the heating power
461 and the room temperature of these distillations. The measured head temperature had
462 practically the same evolution in all runs despite different evolutions of the environmental
463 temperature. Run 1 showed greater differences when compared to run 2 and 3. Small
464 variations in the manipulated variable efficiently compensated these disturbances, like the
465 alembic distillation system in Luna et al. (2018). Figure S8 and S9 compare simulations with
466 experimental values of the w13 strategy. This strategy was completed in 45 min (including
467 head and heart cuts). Alcoholic strength, head temperature and distillate volume were
468 predicted well. Acetaldehyde, methanol, ethyl acetate, linalool and β -phenylethanol
469 predictions were inside the confidence intervals in the head and heart fractions. Model
470 predictions of hexanoic acid during the head and heart cuts were below the experimental
471 values. The results of the calibration distillations showed a similar behavior.

472 **3.4 Multi-objective weighting function based PCA decomposition (MO2) and** 473 **experimental validation**

474 Table 4 shows the MO2 optimization results, including PCA_1 and PCA_2 optimal coordinates,
475 PCA_1 and PCA_2 target coordinates, as well as the head and heart cut volumes, ethanol
476 recovery and relative concentrations of acetaldehyde, linalool and β -phenylethanol of the
477 heart fraction. Figure 2 shows the optimal values of the congeners in the PCA map for each
478 optimization case including both methods: the multi-objective weighting function based on
479 PCA decomposition (see Table 4) and the multi-objective weighting function based on
480 chemical markers (see Table 3).

481 The MO2 strategy achieved good approximations to commercial distillates PCh3, PCh5,
482 PCh6 and PCh8, which were shown previously to be in the reachable space of the alembic's
483 model (see Figure 1). However, the PCh4 distillate was the hardest to reproduce via
484 simulations since this zone of the PCA map is rich in linalool and poor in acetaldehyde. In
485 addition, as discussed above, when linalool is maximized (desirable value) acetaldehyde is
486 also maximized (undesirable value), as they are competing objectives. Thus, our simulation
487 of the PCh4 distillate required a high rectification, yielding a low productivity, with higher
488 ethanol recovery in the head-cut (53.8%) than in the heart-cut (38.2%).

489 The heating power paths were very different in each evaluated case. Figure 3 shows the
490 optimum trajectories of the heating power, the head temperature and the alcoholic strength
491 obtained for optimal cases PCh6 and PCh8. PCh4 strategy yielded the fastest distillation
492 coinciding with the lowest amount of tail compounds (64.4 of methanol, 0.292 of hexanoic
493 acid and 0.443 of β -phenylethanol in g/hLa.a.) as shown in Table S2. Conversely, strategy
494 PCh6 yielded the largest heart volume (460.1 mL) and longest distillation, coinciding with a
495 higher amount of tail compounds (82.8 of methanol, 0.774 of hexanoic acid and 1.91 β -
496 phenylethanol in g/hLa.a.) as shown in Table S2. In addition, strategy PCh8 yielded the
497 smallest head-cut (95.4 mL), the highest ethanol recovery in the heart-cut (70.2%) and the
498 highest acetaldehyde concentration (25.5 g/hLa.a.), which is 65-80% more than PCh3, PCh5
499 and PCh6 (Table S2).

500 Finally, the optimal PCh6 strategy was carried out experimentally to validate the alembic
501 model. Figure 4 shows how the heating power was adapted to track the optimal set-point
502 despite the room temperature disturbances. This distillation lasted 80 min and was more
503 reproducible than the w13 distillation. Figures 5 and 6 show that alcohol strength, distillate

504 volume, head temperature and most congeners were well predicted. Only hexanoic acid
505 predictions were biased, like in the calibration experiments (250 W and 450 W strategies); in
506 this case the thermodynamic model used is probably unsuitable.

507 **3.5 Comparison of multi-objective function MO1 and MO2**

508 Figure 7 shows the Pareto front (acetaldehyde vs linalool) according to the MO1 results (see
509 section 3.3). The upper part of the Pareto front corresponds to optimization runs with β and
510 γ values higher than α . In these distillations, the heating power was kept constant at the lower
511 limit (250 W). The lower part of the Pareto front corresponds to optimization runs with α
512 values higher than β and γ . Figure 7 also includes the MO2 results, showing that many
513 principal component optimization strategies (opt PCh3, opt PCh4, opt PCh5 and opt PCh6)
514 lie close to the lower part of the Pareto front, defined by high values of α . Moreover, many
515 of the commercial piscos analyzed (PCh2, PCh3, PCh5, PCh6, PCh7 and PCh8) lie in this
516 zone. For example, commercial pisco PCh7 lies in the Pareto front and contains practically
517 the same linalool and acetaldehyde concentrations as the w7 optimal solution from MO1 and
518 PCh4 optimal solution of MO2. Many commercial distillates coincided with optimal
519 strategies in the Pareto front, meaning that the skills and years of experience of the pisco
520 distillers were able to reach optimal distilling conditions.

521 Validation experiments of w13 and PCh6 strategies confirmed that maximizing linalool
522 concentrations implies minimizing β -phenylethanol concentrations (harmonic objectives)
523 and minimizing acetaldehyde concentrations (competitive objectives) in the heart cut. A fast
524 distillation strategy like w13 obtained high concentrations of linalool and head compounds
525 like acetaldehyde and ethyl acetate, and low concentrations of tail compounds such as
526 methanol and β -phenylethanol (see Table S3). Conversely, slow distillations like PCh6,

527 yielded low concentrations of acetaldehyde and linalool, and high concentrations of tail
528 compounds (see Table S4).

529 Both validation experiments lie far from the Pareto front, while the corresponding
530 simulations are located exactly in the Pareto front (Figure S10). In both experimental cases,
531 more acetaldehyde and less linalool than predicted were obtained, although PCh6 simulations
532 were closer to measured values than w13 predictions. Predictions of the rest of the congeners
533 were also biased, except the methanol predictions that were quite accurate. Experiments w13
534 and PCh6 were recalibrated to verify if the model could fit the observations better; calibrated
535 parameters are shown in Table S5. UA_b and UA_c parameters showed the most significant
536 differences with those calibrated in section 3.1. These new parameters were smaller than
537 those calibrated originally, since environmental temperatures and distillation times were
538 different than those of the calibration experiments. The new simulations (w13 cal and PCh6
539 cal) lie in the Pareto front close to the original simulations, without significant improvement
540 in fitting the measured values (Figure S10). Therefore, a better model relating the heating
541 power and the heat transfer parameters should be developed to improve the predictive ability
542 of the alembic model under varying heating power operation.

543 MO1 optimizations yielded a wider range of solutions than MO2, although the latter
544 approach was more suitable to attain defined targets. In addition, MO2 contains more
545 information regarding the aromatic composition of the distillates and this procedure can be
546 expanded easily to many more components.

547 **4 CONCLUSIONS**

548 Volume cuts have a greater effect on the quality aroma profile of the distillates than the
549 distillation rates. Multivariable analysis (PCA) was useful to compare commercial piscos

550 with the distillates obtained with our model-based design approach. Two multi-objective
551 functions were applied in the dynamic optimization design of batch distillation recipes. In
552 Multi-objective weighting functions based on chemical markers (MO1), minimization of
553 head cut markers such as acetaldehyde or ethyl acetate (off flavors) conflict with
554 maximization of heart cut makers such as linalool and with the minimization of tail cut
555 markers such as hexanoic acid or β -phenylethanol. Since the maximization of heart cut
556 markers is harmonic with the minimization of tail cut markers, only two objectives were
557 necessary to define the Pareto front of the MO1 optimization approach. This optimization
558 approach allowed us to explore the alembic reachable space better, although simulations were
559 not able to predict well the MO1 experimental distillation. Multi-objective optimization
560 based on PCA decomposition (MO2) used all the chemical composition available and
561 allowed us to attain a defined target easily if that target is reachable by the alembic. Moreover,
562 MO2 simulations were closer to measured values. Some commercial distillates lay close to
563 the Pareto front; hence, distillers, with skill and experience, were able to produce near optimal
564 distillates.

565 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**

566 RL appreciates a PhD and internship scholarship from CONICYT- PCHA/Doctorado
567 Nacional/2014-21140890 to develop this work during his stay at the Universitat Rovira i
568 Virgili. JRP is grateful to Universidad Federal de Santa Catarina (UFSC) and Pontificia
569 Universidad Católica de Chile that supported his sabbatical leave at UFSC. We are grateful
570 to Lisa Gingles who reviewed the English grammar of the manuscript.

571 **Appendix A. Congeners Modeling**

572 This is an extension of the binary ethanol-water model available in appendix of Luna et al.
573 (2018). According to the pseudo binary assumption in Sacher et al. (2013) model, given the
574 very low concentrations of the congeners, it is assumed that they do not influence the
575 equilibrium temperature, enthalpy and physical properties of the mixture. Each congener is
576 added to the model through the respective mass balance.

577 Boiler component balance

$$\frac{d(M_B \cdot x_{B,cong})}{dt} = L \cdot x_{L,cong} - V_B \cdot y_{B,cong} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

578

579 Partial condenser component balance

$$V_B \cdot y_{B,cong} - L \cdot x_{L,cong} - V_D \cdot y_{D,cong} = 0 \quad (\text{A.2})$$

580

581 Distillate component balance

$$\frac{dM_{cong}}{dt} = y_{D,cong} \cdot V_D \quad (\text{A.3})$$

582

583 Thermodynamic equilibrium relationships of congeners

$$y_{D,cong} = K_{C,cong} \cdot x_{L,cong} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

584

$$y_{B,cong} = K_{B,cong} \cdot x_{B,cong} \quad (A.5)$$

585

$$x_{L,cong} = \frac{V_B K_{B,cong} x_{B,cong}}{L + V_D K_{C,cong}} \quad (A.6)$$

586

587 Congener equilibrium relationship

588 The equilibrium constant is calculated by the extended Raoult's law

$$y_{cong} \cdot P = x_{cong} \cdot P_{cong}^{LV} \cdot \gamma_{cong} \quad (A.7)$$

589

590 The partition coefficient is

$$K_{cong} = \frac{y_{cong}}{x_{cong}} = \frac{P_{cong}^{LV} \cdot \gamma_{cong}}{P} \quad (A.8)$$

591

592 The activity coefficient for congeners γ_{cong} were estimated using the UNIFAC contribution

593 groups method. Table A.1 Shows the UNIFAC groups of six congeners used in this work and

594 their Antoine parameters to calculate the vapor pressure. Given the negligible congener

595 concentrations according to the quasi-binary assumption, the activity coefficient, the vapor

596 pressure and equilibrium temperatures is assumed dependent on the ethanol composition only

$$K_{cong} = \frac{y_{cong}}{x_{cong}} = \frac{P_{cong}^{LV}(x_{eth}) \cdot \gamma_{cong}(x_{eth})}{P} = K_{cong}(x_{eth}) \quad (A.9)$$

597

598 In order to accelerate the CPU time during the integration in the parameter's estimation and
599 dynamic optimization, this function is approximated with a 6 order polynomial.

600

$$K_{cong} = p_{1,cong}x_{eth}^6 + p_{2,cong}x_{eth}^5 + p_{3,cong}x_{eth}^4 + p_{4,cong}x_{eth}^3 + p_{5,cong}x_{eth}^2 + p_{7,cong} \quad (A.1)$$

601

602

603 REFERENCES

604 Agosin, E., Belancic, A., Ibacache, A., Baumes, R., Bordeu, E., Crawford, A., Bayonove, C.,
605 2000. Aromatic potential of certain Muscat grape varieties important for Pisco
606 production in Chile. *Am. J. Enol. Vitic.* 51, 404–408.

607 Arrieta-Garay, Y., García-Llobodanin, L., Pérez-Correa, J.R., López-Vázquez, C., Orriols,
608 I., López, F., 2013. Aromatically enhanced pear distillates from blanquilla and
609 conference varieties using a packed column. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 61, 4936–4942.

610 Barton, P.I., Allgor, R.J., Feehery, W.F., Galán, S., 1998. Dynamic Optimization in a
611 Discontinuous World. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 37, 966–981.

612 Bhaskar, V., Gupta, S.K., Ray, A.K., 2000. Applications of Multiobjective Optimization in
613 Chemical Engineering. *Rev. Chem. Eng.* 16, 1–54.

614 Biblioteca del congreso nacional de Chile, Ministerio de Agricultura, 2012. Biblioteca del
615 Congreso Nacional de Chile - www.leychile.cl - documento generado el 24-Nov-2012.
616 Reglam. Ley N° 18.455 que fija normas sobre Prod. Elabor. y Comer. alcoholes etilicos,

617 bebidas alcohólicas y vinages.

618 Bonilla-Petriciolet, A., Rangaiah, G.P., 2013. Introduction, in: *Multi-Objective Optimization*
619 *in Chemical Engineering*. Wiley-Blackwell, pp. 1–16.

620 Bordiga, M., Rinaldi, M., Locatelli, M., Piana, G., Travaglia, F., Coisson, J.D., Arlorio, M.,
621 2013. Characterization of Muscat wines aroma evolution using comprehensive gas
622 chromatography followed by a post-analytic approach to 2D contour plots comparison.
623 *Food Chem.* 140, 57–67.

624 Byers, J.A., 1997. Vapor pressure of Volatile Chemicals [WWW Document]. URL
625 <http://www.chemical-ecology.net/java/jav-vp.htm> (accessed 9.5.18).

626 Cacho, J., Moncayo, L., Palma, J.C., Ferreira, V., Culleré, L., 2012. Characterization of the
627 aromatic profile of the Italia variety of Peruvian pisco by gas chromatography-
628 olfactometry and gas chromatography coupled with flame ionization and mass
629 spectrometry detection systems. *Food Res. Int.* 49, 117–125.

630 Carvalho, J., Labbe, M., Pérez-Correa, J.R., Zaror, C., Wisniak, J., 2011. Modelling methanol
631 recovery in wine distillation stills with packing columns. *Food Control* 22, 1322–1332.

632 Christoph, N., Bauer-Christoph, C., 2007. Flavour of Spirit Drinks: Raw Materials,
633 Fermentation, Distillation, and Ageing, in: Berger, R.G. (Ed.), *Flavours and Fragrances:*
634 *Chemistry, Bioprocessing and Sustainability*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin,
635 Heidelberg, pp. 219–239.

636 Claus, M.J., Berglund, K.A., 2009. Defining still parameters using CHEMCAD batch
637 distillation model for modeling fruit spirits distillations. *J. Food Process Eng.* 32, 881–
638 892.

639 Clutton, D.W., Evans, M.B., 1978. The flavour constituents of gin. *J. Chromatogr. A* 167,
640 409–419.

641 De Lucca, F., Munizaga-Miranda, R., Jopia-Castillo, D., Gelmi, C. a., Pérez-Correa, J.R.,
642 2013. Operation Strategies to Minimize Methanol Recovery in Batch Distillation of
643 Hydroalcoholic Mixtures. *Int. J. Food Eng.* 9, 259–265.

644 Diwekar, U., 1995. *Batch Distillation: Simulation, Optimal Design, And Control*, Series in
645 chemical and mechanical engineering. Taylor & Francis.

646 Egea, J. a., Rodríguez-Fernández, M., Banga, J.R., Martí, R., 2007. Scatter search for
647 chemical and bio-process optimization. *J. Glob. Optim.* 37, 481–503.

648 Esteban-Decloux, M., Deterre, S., Kadir, S., Giampaoli, P., Albet, J., Joulia, X., Baudouin,
649 O., 2014. Two industrial examples of coupling experiments and simulations for
650 increasing quality and yield of distilled beverages. *Food Bioprod. Process.* 92, 343–354.

651 Ferreira, V., López, R., Escudero, A., Cacho, J.F., 1998. Quantitative determination of trace
652 and ultratrace flavour active compounds in red wines through gas chromatographic-ion
653 trap mass spectrometric analysis of microextracts. *J. Chromatogr. A* 806, 349–354.

654 García-Llobodanin, L., Roca, J., López, J.R., Pérez-Correa, J.R., López, F., 2011. The lack
655 of reproducibility of different distillation techniques and its impact on pear spirit
656 composition. *Int. J. Food Sci. Technol.* 46, 1956–1963.

657 Hedengren, J.D., Shishavan, R.A., Powell, K.M., Edgar, T.F., 2014. Nonlinear modeling,
658 estimation and predictive control in APMonitor. *Comput. Chem. Eng.* 70, 133–148.

659 Jolliffe, I.T., 2002. *Principal Component Analysis*, Second Edition, Encyclopedia of

660 Statistics in Behavioral Science.

661 Kameswaran, S., Biegler, L.T., 2006. Simultaneous dynamic optimization strategies: Recent
662 advances and challenges. *Comput. Chem. Eng.* 30, 1560–1575.

663 López, F., Rodríguez-Bencomo, J.J., Orriols, I., Pérez-Correa, J.R., 2017. Chapter 10 - Fruit
664 Brandies, in: Kosseva, M.R., Joshi, V.K., Panesar, P.S. (Eds.), *Science and Technology
665 of Fruit Wine Production*. Academic Press, San Diego, pp. 531–556.

666 Luna, R., López, F., Pérez-Correa, J.R., 2018. Minimizing methanol content in experimental
667 charentais alembic distillations. *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* 57.

668 Matias-Guiu, P., Rodríguez-Bencomo, J.J., Orriols, I., Pérez-Correa, J.R., López, F., 2016.
669 Floral aroma improvement of Muscat spirits by packed column distillation with variable
670 internal reflux. *Food Chem.* 213, 40–48.

671 Matias-Guiu, P., Rodríguez-Bencomo, J.J., Pérez-Correa, J.R., López, F., 2018. Aroma
672 profile design of wine spirits: Multi-objective optimization using response surface
673 methodology. *Food Chem.* 245, 1087–1097.

674 Miettinen, K., Hakanen, J., 2009. Why Use Interactive Multi-Objective Optimization in
675 Chemical Process Design. *Multi-Objective Optim. Tech. Appl. Chem. Eng.* 153–188.

676 Mujtaba, I.M., 2004. *Batch Distillation: Design and Operation*, Chemical engineering.
677 Imperial College Press.

678 Osorio, D., Pérez-Correa, J.R., Biegler, L.T., Agosin, E., 2005. Wine distillates: Practical
679 operating recipe formulation for stills. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 53, 6326–6331.

680 Osorio, D., Pérez-Correa, R., Belancic, A., Agosin, E., 2004. Rigorous dynamic modeling

681 and simulation of wine distillations. *Food Control* 15, 515–521.

682 Pozo, C., Ruíz-Femenia, R., Caballero, J., Guillén-Gosálbez, G., Jiménez, L., 2012. On the
683 use of Principal Component Analysis for reducing the number of environmental
684 objectives in multi-objective optimization: Application to the design of chemical supply
685 chains. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 69, 146–158.

686 Puentes, C., Joulia, X., Vidal, J.P., Esteban-Decloux, M., 2018. Simulation of spirits
687 distillation for a better understanding of volatile aroma compounds behavior:
688 Application to Armagnac production. *Food Bioprod. Process.* 112, 31–62.

689 Rodríguez-Bencomo, J.J., Pérez-Correa, J.R., Orriols, I., López, F., 2016. Spirit Distillation
690 Strategies for Aroma Improvement Using Variable Internal Column Reflux. *Food*
691 *Bioprocess Technol.* 9, 1885–1892.

692 Sacher, J., García-Llobodanin, L., López, F., Segura, H., Pérez-Correa, J.R., 2017. The Spirit
693 World: Can chemical engineering help spirits distillers close the loop between historic
694 roots and modern modelling methods? *Chem. Eng.* 32–35.

695 Sacher, J., García-Llobodanin, L., López, F., Segura, H., Pérez-Correa, J.R., 2013. Dynamic
696 modeling and simulation of an alembic pear wine distillation. *Food Bioprod. Process.*
697 91, 447–456.

698 Safdarnejad, S.M., Hedengren, J.D., Lewis, N.R., Haseltine, E.L., 2015. Initialization
699 strategies for optimization of dynamic systems. *Comput. Chem. Eng.* 78, 39–50.

700 Scanavini, H.F. a, Ceriani, R., Cassini, C.E.B., Souza, E.L.R., Maugeri Filho, F., Meirelles,
701 A.J. a, 2010. Cachaça production in a lab-scale alembic: Modeling and computational
702 simulation. *J. Food Process Eng.* 33, 226–252.

703 Scanavini, H.F. a, Ceriani, R., Meirelles, a. J. a, 2012. Cachaça distillation investigated on
704 the basis of model systems. *Brazilian J. Chem. Eng.* 29, 429–440.

705 Sharma, S., Rangaiah, G.P., 2013. Multi-Objective Optimization Applications in Chemical
706 Engineering, in: *Multi-Objective Optimization in Chemical Engineering*. Wiley-
707 Blackwell, pp. 35–102.

708 Small, R.W., Couturier, M., Godfrey, M., 2011. *Beverage Basics: Understanding and*
709 *Appreciating Wine, Beer, and Spirits*. Wiley.

710 Spaho, N., 2017. Distillation Techniques in the Fruit Spirits Production, in: Mendes, M.F.
711 (Ed.), *Distillation - Innovative Applications and Modeling*. InTech, Rijeka.

712 Spaho, N., Dürr, P., Grba, S., Velagić-Habul, E., Blesić, M., 2013. Effects of distillation cut
713 on the distribution of higher alcohols and esters in brandy produced from three plum
714 varieties. *J. Inst. Brew.* 119, 48–56.

715 Srinivasan, B., Bonvin, D., Visser, E., Palanki, S., 2003. Dynamic optimization of batch
716 processes. *Comput. Chem. Eng.* 27, 27–44.

717 Tsakiris, A., Kallithraka, S., Kourkoutas, Y., 2014. Grape brandy production, composition
718 and sensory evaluation. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 94, 404–414.

719 Valderrama, J.O., Toselli, L.A., Faúndez, C.A., 2012. Advances on modeling and simulation
720 of alcoholic distillation. Part 2: Process simulation. *Food Bioprod. Process.* 90, 832–
721 840.

722 Vassiliadis, V.S., Sargent, R.W.H., Pantelides, C.C., 1994a. Solution of a Class of Multistage
723 Dynamic Optimization Problems. 1. Problems without Path Constraints. *Ind. Eng.*

- 724 Chem. Res. 33, 2111–2122.
- 725 Vassiliadis, V.S., Sargent, R.W.H., Pantelides, C.C., 1994b. Solution of a Class of Multistage
726 Dynamic Optimization Problems. 2. Problems with Path Constraints. Ind. Eng. Chem.
727 Res. 33, 2123–2133.
- 728 Weise, T., 2008. Global Optimization Algorithms - Theory and Applications.
- 729
- 730
- 731

Table 1. Congeners concentration and their properties in synthetic and Muscat wines

N_{cong}	Congener	Molar Weight (g/mol)	Synthetic wine		Muscat wine		Odor	Odor threshold (g/hL.a.a.)
			Concentration (mg/L)	Molar fraction (mol/mol)	Concentration (mg/L)	Molar fraction (mol/mol)		
Head compounds								
1	Acetaldehyde	44.1	162	7.16e-05	179	7.87e-05	Pungent	25 ^a
2	Methanol	32.0	88.9	5.39e-05	82.7	5.01e-05	Toxic	167 ^a
3	Ethyl acetate	88.1	70.4	1.55e-05	81.3	1.79e-05	Glue	12.5 ^b
Terpenic compound								
4	Linalool	154	1.01	1.27e-07	1.11	1.39e-07	Muscat	0.25 ^c
Tail compounds								
5	Hexanoic acid	116	8.01	1.34e-06	6.57	1.10e-06	Rancid	2 ^a
6	β -Phenylethanol	122	31.5	5.00e-06	26.8	4.26e-06	Roses, floral	5 ^c

733 ^a Referenced in Christoph and Bauer-Christoph (2007).734 ^b Referenced in Clutton and Evans (1978).735 ^c Referenced in Cacho et al. (2012).

736

Table 2. Fitted parameters for distillation strategies

Parameters	Strategies			
	250W	450W	PCh6	W13
UA_b	0.82 ± 0.04	0.71 ± 0.10	b	b
UA_c	1.28 ± 0.05	1.73 ± 0.17	c	c
M_0	93.5 ± 0.3	93.6 ± 0.3	93.3 ± 0.4	93.3 ± 0.2
x_0	0.033 ± 0.0002	0.033 ± 0.0003	0.033 ± 0.0001	0.030 ± 0.0004
$x_{0,cong} = 1$	$2.37e-5 \pm 0.30e-5$	$2.55e-5 \pm 0.17e-5$	$3.04e-5 \pm 0.33e-5$	$2.45e-5 \pm 0.30e-5$
$x_{0,cong} = 2$	$3.18e-5 \pm 0.10e-5$	$3.60e-5 \pm 0.096e-5$	$4.91e-5 \pm 0.14e-5$	$4.33e-5 \pm 0.11e-5$
$x_{0,cong} = 3$	$2.95e-6 \pm 0.37e-6$	$3.18e-06 \pm 0.17e-6$	$3.83e-6 \pm 0.54e-6$	$2.92e-6 \pm 0.87e-6$
$x_{0,cong} = 4$	$5.78e-8 \pm 0.24e-8$	$6.33e-08 \pm 0.38e-8$	$4.10e-8 \pm 0.50e-8$	$3.41e-8 \pm 0.53e-8$
$x_{0,cong} = 5$	$1.33e-6 \pm 0.001e-6$	$1.33e-06 \pm 0.01e-6$	$1.33e-6 \pm 0.003e-6$	$1.32e-6 \pm 0.02e-6$
$x_{0,cong} = 6$	$2.43e-6 \pm 0.021e-6$	$2.92e-06 \pm 0.12e-6$	$3.17e-6 \pm 0.10e-6$	$2.30e-6 \pm 0.08e-6$

737

^a Parameters unit: UA_b and UA_c in $W/^\circ C$, M_0 in mol, x_0 and $x_{0,cong}$ in mol/mol.

738

^{b, c} linear function between UA_b and UA_c values obtained from 250 and 450W respectively.

739

Table 3. Results obtained of multi-objective weighting function based on chemical markers in the heart cut

Run	α	β	γ	J_1	Volume head (mL)	Volume heart (mL)	Ethanol recovery (%)	C_{acet}		C_{lin}		$C_{\beta-feOH}$		PCA_1	PCA_2
								g/hLa.a.	OAV ^a	g/hLa.a.	OAV ^a	g/hLa.a.	OAV ^a		
w1	1	0	0	2.170	248.7	483.6	35.2	0.70	0.03	0.061	0.24	43.92	8.78	6.7149	-0.5228
w2	0.8	0.2	0	2.094	249.7	456.9	35.2	0.74	0.03	0.063	0.25	42.41	8.48	6.1376	-0.5987
w7	0.8	0	0.2	0.916	188.7	241.3	40.3	3.51	0.14	0.163	0.65	19.48	3.90	-0.7045	0.3436
w3	0.6	0.4	0	0.788	168.6	241.4	44.4	6.64	0.27	0.232	0.93	17.21	3.44	-1.3241	0.7099
w12	0.6	0	0.4	0.630	129.7	236.0	49.4	14.89	0.60	0.360	1.44	14.23	2.85	-1.9130	1.5723
w8	0.6	0.2	0.2	0.634	131.6	237.8	49.3	15.08	0.60	0.363	1.45	14.29	2.86	-1.8765	1.5895
w9	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.586	101.5	252.9	55.3	27.94	1.12	0.492	1.97	12.91	2.58	-1.5663	2.6575
w16	0.4	0	0.6	0.525	99.3	217.5	50.6	28.21	1.13	0.514	2.05	11.88	2.38	-1.9286	2.7492
w13	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.555	81.6	245.4	57.5	39.85	1.59	0.590	2.36	11.70	2.34	-1.0991	3.5516
w4	0.4	0.6	0	0.545	80.8	239.2	56.4	41.14	1.65	0.605	2.42	11.47	2.29	-1.0835	3.6643
w19	0.2	0	0.8	0.545	57.8	206.8	53.9	71.60	2.86	0.825	3.30	9.60	1.92	0.9272	5.6770
w17	0.2	0.2	0.6	0.556	55.0	206.2	54.1	76.39	3.06	0.852	3.41	9.47	1.89	1.3679	5.9496
w5	0.2	0.8	0	0.601	46.8	205.4	54.7	91.46	3.66	0.930	3.72	9.12	1.82	2.8929	6.7393
w6	0	1	0	0.601	46.8	205.4	54.7	91.46	3.66	0.930	3.72	9.12	1.82	2.8929	6.7393
w10	0.2	0.6	0.2	0.601	46.8	205.4	54.7	91.46	3.66	0.930	3.72	9.12	1.82	2.8929	6.7393
w11	0	0.8	0.2	0.601	46.8	205.4	54.7	91.46	3.66	0.930	3.72	9.12	1.82	2.8929	6.7393
w14	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.601	46.8	205.4	54.7	91.46	3.66	0.930	3.72	9.12	1.82	2.8929	6.7393
w15	0	0.6	0.4	0.601	46.8	205.4	54.7	91.46	3.66	0.930	3.72	9.12	1.82	2.8929	6.7393
w18	0	0.4	0.6	0.601	46.8	205.4	54.7	91.46	3.66	0.930	3.72	9.12	1.82	2.8929	6.7393
w20	0	0.2	0.8	0.601	46.8	205.4	54.7	91.46	3.66	0.930	3.72	9.12	1.82	2.8929	6.7393
w21	0	0	1	0.601	46.8	205.4	54.7	91.46	3.66	0.930	3.72	9.12	1.82	2.8929	6.7393

741 ^aOdor activity value expressed in units of aroma (u.a.) were calculated by dividing the congeners concentrations in g/hLa.a. of this
742 table by respective odor threshold in Table 1.

744

Table 4. Results obtained of multi-objective weighting function based on PCA decomposition

Target of multi-objective optimization	Simulated									Target			
	Volume head (mL)	Volume heart (mL)	Ethanol recovery (%)	C_{acet}		C_{lin}		$C_{\beta-feOH}$		PCA_1	PCA_2	PCA_1	PCA_2
				g/hLa.a.	OAV ^a	g/hLa.a.	OAV ^a	g/hLa.a.	OAV ^a				
Optimal PCh3	143.2	449.8	58.9	9.66	0.39	0.260	1.04	25.1	5.02	1.0323	0.6233	0.9866	0.5643
Optimal PCh4	200.0	220.8	38.2	3.22	0.13	0.157	0.63	19.1	3.82	-0.8552	0.2964	-1.0124	-0.1676
Optimal PCh5	127.9	408.2	60.3	11.3	0.45	0.284	1.14	21.7	4.34	0.1665	0.9292	0.1375	0.9409
Optimal PCh6	157.3	460.1	55.1	6.53	0.26	0.212	0.85	27.8	5.56	1.6856	0.2637	1.6299	0.1998
Optimal PCh8	95.4	424.8	70.2	27.7	1.11	0.442	1.77	18.8	3.76	0.2802	2.2689	0.1664	2.2484

745 ^aOdor activity value expressed in units of aroma (u.a.) were calculated by dividing the congeners concentrations in g/hLa.a. of this

746 table by respective odor threshold in Table 1.

747

748

749

750

751

752

753

Table A.1. Thermodynamic properties of congeners.

Congener	Structure	UNIFAC groups	Antoine parameters		
			A (mmHg)	B (mmHg K)	C (K)
Acetaldehyde		1 CH3 1 CHO	16.248	2465.148	-37.150 ^a
Methanol		1 CH3OH	18.533	3600.017	-35.171 ^a
Ethyl acetate		1 CH3 1 CH2 1 CH3COO	16.182	2763.631	-60.926 ^a
Linalool		3 CH3 3 CH2 2 CH 2 C 1 OH	19.705	6110.099	-2.32 ^b
Hexanoic acid		1 CH3 4 CH2 1 COOH	23.662	7825.227	-9.0018 ^b
β -Phenylethanol		5 ACH 1 AC 2 CH2 1 OH	21.753	7273.03	0 ^a

755 ^aData from Sacher et al. (2013).756 ^bChemical ecology database (Byers, 1997).

757

758

759

760

761

762

763

764 **Figure 1.** PCA map in two principal components: Simulations with random heating power
765 path and random head and heart cuts (\blacktriangle). Simulations with random heating power path and
766 fixed head and heart cuts (\times). Simulations with fixed heating power path and random head
767 and heart cuts ($+$). Blue points correspond to the commercial piscos.

768 **Figure 2.** PCA map in two principal components: distillate target optimal points by MO2
769 and weight optimal points by MO1 (black points), and Chilean commercial piscos (blue
770 points).

771 **Figure 3.** Heating power, head temperature and alcoholic strength vs time. PCh6 strategy
772 (a), PCh8 strategy (b), head fraction (HD) and heart fraction (HT). Heating power ($-$), head
773 temperature ($-$) and alcoholic strength ($:$).

774 **Figure 4.** Experimental PCh6 optimal strategy in triplicate. Top figure: head temperature set
775 point (sky blue solid line), measured temperatures; run 1 (black dotted lines), run 2 (gray
776 dotted lines) and run 3 (red dotted lines). Bottom Figures: heating power path and room
777 temperature; run 1 (black solid line), run 2 (gray solid line) and run 3 (red solid line).

778 **Figure 5.** Alcoholic strength (%v/v), head temperature and distillate volume vs time for an
779 optimal PCh6 strategy. Experimental data; run 1 (\times), run 2 (Δ) and run 3 (\circ). Simulation ($-$
780) and confidence interval ($--$).

781 **Figure 6.** Congeners concentrations (g/hL.a.a.) vs time for an optimal PCh6 strategy.
782 Experimental data; run 1 (\times), run 2 (Δ) and run 3 (\circ). Simulation ($-$) and confidence
783 interval ($--$).

784 **Figure 7.** Pareto front: relative acetaldehyde concentration vs relative linalool concentration;
785 weight optimal points by MO1 (black triangles), distilled target optimal points by MO2 (red

786 squares) and Chilean commercial distillates (blue circles). Note that the concentrations of
787 linalool are plotted with negative values to preserve the usual shape of Pareto front figures.

788

Optimal strategy PCh6

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

QUALITY AROMA IMPROVEMENT OF MUSCAT WINE SPIRITS: A NEW APPROACH USING FIRST-PRINCIPLES MODEL-BASED DESIGN AND MULTI-OBJECTIVE DYNAMIC OPTIMIZATION THROUGH MULTI-VARIABLE ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

Ricardo Luna ^a, Pau Matias-Guiu ^b, Francisco López ^b, José R. Pérez-Correa ^{a,c *}.

^a Departamento de Ingeniería Química y Bioprocesos, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Vicuña Mackenna 4860, Casilla 306, Santiago 22, Chile, rlluna@uc.cl

^b Departament d'Enginyeria Química, Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Av. Països Catalans 26, 43007, Tarragona, Spain, pau.matiasguiu@urv.cat, francisco.lopez@urv.cat

^c Departamento de Automação e Sistemas, Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Centro Tecnológico, Bairro Trindade, Caixa Postal 476, Florianópolis-SC, 88040-900, Brazil.

Corresponding author José R. Pérez-Correa: perez@ing.puc.cl; phone: +562-23544258

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Figure S1. Principal component analysis (PCA) applied to data of Chilean commercial piscos.

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Figure S2. PCA map of two principal components: Simulations with 19 time intervals (▲). Simulations with 9 time intervals (×). Simulations with 4 time intervals (+). Blue points correspond to the commercial Chilean piscos.

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Figure S3. Alcoholic strength (%v/v), head temperature and distillate volume vs time for a constant heating power rate of 450W. Experimental data; run 1 (\times), run 2 (Δ) and run 3 (\circ). Simulation (—) and confidence interval (---).

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Figure S4. Congeners concentrations (g/hL.a.a.) vs time for a constant heating power rate of 450W. Experimental data; run 1 (×), run 2 (Δ) and run 3 (○). Simulation (—) and confidence interval (---).

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Figure S5. Alcoholic strength (%v/v), head temperature and distillate volume vs time for a constant heating power rate of 250W. Experimental data; run 1 (\times), run 2 (Δ) and run 3 (\circ). Simulation (—) and confidence interval (---).

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Figure S6. Congeners concentrations (g/hL.a.a.) vs time for a constant heating power rate of 250W. Experimental data; run 1 (×), run 2 (Δ) and run 3 (○). Simulation (—) and confidence interval (---).

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Figure S7. Experimental w13 optimal strategy in triplicate. Top figure: head temperature set point (sky blue solid line), measured temperatures; run 1 (black dotted lines), run 2 (gray dotted lines) and run 3 (red dotted lines). Bottom Figures: heating power path and room temperature; run 1 (black solid line), run 2 (gray solid line) and run 3 (red solid line).

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Figure S8. Alcoholic strength (%v/v), head temperature and distillate volume vs time for an optimal w13 strategy. Experimental data; run 1 (×), run 2 (Δ) and run 3 (○). Simulation (—) and confidence interval (— —).

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Figure S9. Congeners concentrations (g/hL.a.a) vs time for an optimal w13 strategy. Experimental data; run 1 (\times), run 2 (Δ) and run 3 (\circ). Simulation (—) and confidence interval (---).

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Figure S10. Pareto front: relative acetaldehyde concentration vs relative linalool concentration; weight optimal points by MO1 (black triangles), distilled target optimal points by MO2 (red squares), validation experiments (blue diamonds) and model recalibration (blue circles).

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Table S1. Parameters of calibrated compounds for chemical analysis, ordered according to their chromatographic retention time

Compounds	CAS	Supplier company	Minimum assay (%)	Calculated Kovats retention index
Acetaldehyde	75-07-0	Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, USA	99.5	730
Ethyl acetate	141-78-6	Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, USA	99.0	878
Methanol	67-56-1	PanReac Química, S.A.U. Castellar del Vallès, Spain	99.9	917
2-octanol	123-96-6	Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, USA	97.0	1408
Linalool	78-70-6	Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, USA	97.0	1540
Hexanoic acid	142-62-1	Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, USA	98.0	1905
<i>β</i> -phenylethanol	60-12-8	Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, USA	99.0	1949

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Table S2. Congeners concentration in Chilean commercial piscos in g/hL.a.a.

Piscos code	Acetaldehyde	Methanol	Ethyl acetate	Linalool	Hexanoic acid	β - phenylethanol
PCh1	9.06	65.1	11.9	0.789	0.0603	0.0958
PCh2	11.9	83.0	19.3	0.158	0.890	15.0
PCh3	15.3	74.8	16.2	0.0931	0.686	1.77
PCh4	11.9	64.4	16.3	0.457	0.292	0.443
PCh5	14.2	67.0	14.7	0.0874	0.648	1.94
PCh6	15.4	82.8	16.6	0.134	0.774	1.91
PCh7	4.93	65.1	15.0	0.163	0.165	0.392
PCh8	25.5	64.8	14.6	0.121	0.590	1.36
PCh9	3.64	71.5	15.8	0.396	0.136	0.450

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Table S1. Congeners concentration of MO1

Run	Acetaldehyde	Methanol	Ethyl acetate	Linalool	Hexanoic acid	β -phenylethanol
w1	0.70	103.3	0.0050	0.061	3.48	43.92
w2	0.74	102.8	0.0054	0.063	3.22	42.41
w7	3.51	80.35	0.084	0.163	1.04	19.48
w3	6.64	77.39	0.264	0.232	0.867	17.21
w12	14.89	72.86	1.08	0.360	0.677	14.23
w8	15.08	72.92	1.10	0.363	0.690	14.29
w9	27.94	70.63	3.25	0.492	0.613	12.91
w16	28.21	69.08	3.11	0.514	0.534	11.88
w13	39.85	68.74	5.91	0.590	0.525	11.70
w13 exp	63.96	64.92	14.61	0.24	3.96	5.38
w4	41.14	68.35	6.15	0.605	0.517	11.47
w19	71.60	65.36	14.59	0.825	0.404	9.60
w17	76.39	65.12	16.21	0.852	0.397	9.47
w5	91.46	64.52	21.78	0.930	0.380	9.12
w6	91.46	64.52	21.78	0.930	0.380	9.12
w10	91.46	64.52	21.78	0.930	0.380	9.12
w11	91.46	64.52	21.78	0.930	0.380	9.12
w14	91.46	64.52	21.78	0.930	0.380	9.12
w15	91.46	64.52	21.78	0.930	0.380	9.12
w18	91.46	64.52	21.78	0.930	0.380	9.12
w20	91.46	64.52	21.78	0.930	0.380	9.12
w21	91.46	64.52	21.78	0.930	0.380	9.12

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Table S4. Congeners concentration of MO2

Target	Acetaldehyde	Methanol	Ethyl acetate	Linalool	Hexanoic acid	β -phenylethanol
Optimal PCh3	9.67	85.35	0.59	0.260	1.54	25.1
Optimal PCh4	3.22	80.34	0.071	0.157	0.974	19.1
Optimal PCh5	11.3	81.59	0.78	0.284	1.29	21.7
Optimal PCh6	6.53	88.03	0.30	0.212	1.77	27.8
Opt PCh6 exp	18.38	87.81	7.16	0.08	8.88	15.21
Optimal PCh8	27.7	78.14	3.72	0.442	1.06	18.8

Table S5. Fitted parameters for optimal strategies

Parameters ^a	Optimal Strategies	
	PCh6	w13
UA_b	0.283 ± 0.006	0.422 ± 0.065
UA_c	1.13 ± 0.03	1.04 ± 0.06
M_0	93.32 ± 0.18	93.50 ± 0.08
x_0	0.0335 ± 0.0009	0.0335 ± 0.0002
$x_{0,cong} = 1$	$3.49e-5 \pm 0.05e-5$	$3.54e-5 \pm 0.27e-5$
$x_{0,cong} = 2$	$3.97e-5 \pm 0.03e-5$	$4.57e-5 \pm 0.4e-5$
$x_{0,cong} = 3$	$4.75e-6 \pm 0.67e-6$	$4.63e-6 \pm 0.58e-6$
$x_{0,cong} = 4$	$3.89e-8 \pm 0.16e-8$	$3.99e-8 \pm 0.29e-8$
$x_{0,cong} = 5$	$1.31e-6 \pm 0.04e-6$	$1.31e-6 \pm 0.03e-6$
$x_{0,cong} = 6$	$1.59e-6 \pm 0.04e-6$	$2.01e-6 \pm 0.08e-6$

^a Parameters unit: UA_b and UA_c in $W/^\circ C$, M_0 in mol, x_0 and $x_{0,cong}$ in mol/mol.

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

MODELING AND MULTI-OBJECTIVE DYNAMIC OPTIMIZATION OF MUSCAT WINE BATCH DISTILLATIONS

Ricardo Luna ^a, Pau Matias-Guiu ^b, Francisco López ^b, José R. Pérez-Correa ^{a,c *}.

^a Departamento de Ingeniería Química y Bioprocesos, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Vicuña Mackenna 4860, Casilla 306, Santiago 22, Chile, rluna@uc.cl

^b Departament d'Enginyeria Química, Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Av. Països Catalans 26, 43007, Tarragona, Spain, pau.matiasguiu@urv.cat, francisco.lopez@urv.cat

^c Departamento de Automação e Sistemas, Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Centro Tecnológico, Bairro Trindade, Caixa Postal 476, Florianópolis-SC, 88040-900, Brazil.

Corresponding author José R. Pérez-Correa: perez@ing.puc.cl; phone: [+562-23544258](tel:+562-23544258)

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```
function alembic_simulation
% This function contain the routine for simulating an experimental Charentais alembic.
% The model includes ethanol-water plus six congeners.
% This model is useful for any fruit distillate.
% Each congener can be added to the model through the respective mass balance.
% In this model, the equilibrium relationship was calculated using UNIFAC contribution
% group for each congener.
% Author: Ricardo Luna Hernández
% Previous publication with this model:
% Luna, R., López, F., Pérez-Correa, J.R (2018).
% Minimizing methanol content in experimental charentais alembic distillation.
% Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry, 57, 160-170.
% link: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1226086X17304379
clear; clc; close all;
% ===== CONGENER LIST AND INFORMATION =====
% Head compounds
    % Acetaldehyde
    % Methanol
    % Ethyl Acetate
% Terpenic compounds (heart compound)
    % Linalool
% Tail compounds
    % Hexanoic acid
    % b-phenethyl alcohol
% =====
% congeners name
congener_list = {'Acetaldehyde','Methanol','Ethyl acetate',...
    'Linalool','Hexanoic acid','Phenethyl alcohol'};
% congeners molar weight (g/mol)
congener_PM = [44.0526 32.0419 88.1051 154.2493 116.1583 122.1644]';
% number of congeners
Ncong = length(congener_list);
% ===== INITIAL CONDITIONS: CONCENTRATION IN MUSCAT WINE =====
Mb_ini      = 94.9533;          % Molar hold-up in bottom (mol)
xB_ini      = 0.0379;          % Ethanol molar fraction in bottom (mol/mol)
Vd_ini      = 0;                % Distillate volume (mL)
Etdes_ini   = 0;                % Ethanol moles in distillate (mol)
% Congeners molar fraction in bottom (mol/mol)
xB_cong_ini = [7.15699480813622e-05;5.38735319152059e-05; ...
    1.55021174372479e-05;1.26766600263018e-07; ...
    1.33861074704985e-06;5.00325445648047e-06]';
Md_cong_ini = zeros(1,Ncong); % Congeners moles in distillate (mol)
% initial condition vector
x0          = [Mb_ini xB_ini Vd_ini Etdes_ini xB_cong_ini Md_cong_ini];
% initial concentration in wine
```

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```

x0_wine = x0;
% ===== SIMULATION CONFIGURATION =====
% ===== ODE CONFIGURATION =====
% flag_cut
% 1: Normal integration with ODE function (without ODE event).
% 2: Integration with ODE event to make the head and heart cuts.
flag_cut = 1;
% ODE options, tolerances of integration
odeoptions=odeset('Reltol',1e-9,'Abstol',1e-9);
% ===== UA parameter configuration =====
% flag_UA
% 1: linear fuction of heating power
% 2: linear fuction of heating power + 2*sigma
% 3: linear fuction of heating power - 2*sigma
% 4: contant parameters p = [UAb UAc]. This option is usefull to parameter
% estimation
flag_UA = 1;
p = [0.82 0.71];
% ===== MODEL INPUTS =====
% inputs to simulation without cuts (flag_cut = 1)
if flag_cut ==1
    n = 15; % Number of time step(n-1)
    t_end = 120; % Time of distillation (min)
    tspan = linspace(0,t_end,n)*60; % Integration time (s)
    Qcal = ones(length(tspan),1)*300; % Heating power (W)
    T_env = ones(length(tspan),1)*(30+273.15); % Room temperature (K)
    u = [tspan,Qcal,T_env]; % input vector
    V_head = 100;
    V_heart = 400;
% inputs to simulation with cuts, ode event (flag_cut = 2)
elseif flag_cut ==2
    % head cut simulation
    n_head = 4; % Number of time step(n-1)
    V_head = 100; % Volume head (mL)
    t_head = 25; % Time of head cut (min)
    tspan1 = linspace(0,t_head,n_head)*60; % Integration time (s)
    Qcal_head = ones(length(tspan1),1)*300; % Heating power (W)
    T_env1 = ones(length(tspan1),1)*(30+273.15); % Room temperature (K)
    u_head = [tspan1,Qcal_head,T_env1]; % Input vector
    % heart cut simulation
    n_heart = 7; % number of time step(n-1)
    V_heart = 400; % Volume heart (mL)
    t_heart = 120; % Time of heart cut (min)
    tspan2 = linspace(0,t_heart,n_heart)*60; % Integration time (s)
    Qcal_heart = ones(length(tspan2),1)*400; % Heating power (W)
    T_env2 = ones(length(tspan2),1)*(30+273.15); % Room temperature (K)

```

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```

    u_heart    = [tspan2,Qcal_heart,T_env2];          % Input vector
end
% simulation without cuts
% ===== INTEGRATION =====
if flag_cut == 1
    [t,x,TB,TC,F,GAi,GAd,GAd_frac,rec,V,C_cong,C_cong_frac,C_rcong, ...
     C_rcong_frac,rec_cong]= alembic_outputs(Ncong,congener_PM,x0,...
     x0_wine,u,p,odeoptions,flag_UA,flag_cut,V_head,V_heart,'none');
    % simulation with cuts, ode event
elseif flag_cut ==2
    % ===== HEAD INTEGRATION =====
    [time_head,x_head,TB_head,TC_head,F_head,GAi_head,GAd_head, ...
     GAd_head_frac,rec_head,V_head,C_cong_head,C_cong_head_frac, ...
     C_rcong_head,C_rcong_head_frac,rec_cong_head]= ...
     alembic_outputs(Ncong,congener_PM,x0,...
     x0_wine,u_head,p,odeoptions,flag_UA,flag_cut,...
     V_head,V_heart,'head');
    % concatenation the Qcal vector with the time vector, when the simulation
    % was stopped before the time of simulation to make the cut.
    if length(time_head)==(length(tspan1)-1)
        Qcal_head = Qcal_head(1:end-1);
        Qcal_heart(1) = Qcal_head(end);
    elseif length(time_head)==(length(tspan1)-2)
        Qcal_head = Qcal_head(1:end-2);
        Qcal_heart(1) = Qcal_head(end);
    elseif length(time_head)==(length(tspan1)-3)
        Qcal_head = Qcal_head(1:end-3);
        Qcal_heart(1) = Qcal_head(end);
    end
    % initial concentration in heart cut
    x0_heart = x_head(end,:);
    x0_heart([3,4,11,12,13,14,15,16])=0;
    % ===== HEART INTEGRATION =====
    [time_heart,x_heart,TB_heart,TC_heart,F_heart,GAi_heart,GAd_heart, ...
     GAd_heart_frac,rec_heart,V_heart,C_cong_heart,C_cong_heart_frac, ...
     C_rcong_heart,C_rcong_heart_frac,rec_cong_heart]= ...
     alembic_outputs(Ncong,congener_PM,x0_heart,...
     x0_wine,u_heart,p,odeoptions,flag_UA,flag_cut,V_head,V_heart,'heart');
    % concatenation the Qcal vector with the time vector, when the simulation
    % was stopped before the time of simulation to make the cut.
    if length(time_heart) == (length(tspan2)-1)
        Qcal_heart = Qcal_heart(1:end-1);
    elseif length(time_heart) == (length(tspan2)-2)
        Qcal_heart = Qcal_heart(1:end-2);
    elseif length(time_heart) == (length(tspan2)-3)
        Qcal_heart = Qcal_heart(1:end-3);

```

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```
end
% ===== concatenate vector of head and heart cuts =====
time_process=[time_head;time_heart(2:end)+time_head(end)]/60; % time (min)
Qcal_process = [Qcal_head;Qcal_heart(2:end)]; % heating power (w)
TC = [TC_head;TC_heart(2:end)]-273.15; % head temperature (°C)
GAi = [GAi_head;GAi_heart(2:end)]; % instantaneous alcoholic strength
end
% ===== FIGURES AND RESULTS =====
% Results for flag_cut = 1
if flag_cut == 1
% ===== FIGURE 1 =====
figure()
for i =1:Ncong
subplot(2,3,i)
plot(t(2:end)/60,C_rcong_frac(:,i),'-sk')
hold on
plot(t/60,C_rcong(:,i),'-r')
xlabel('Time (min)','FontSize',14)
ylabel('Rel. conc (g/hL.a.a)','FontSize',14)
title([char(congener_list(i)),' in distillate'],'FontSize',12)
set(gca,'FontSize',11);
legend('accumulated in samples collected','accumulated in one sample')
end
% ===== FIGURE 2 =====
figure()
subplot(1,3,1)
plot(t(2:end)/60,GAd_frac,'-sk')
hold on
plot(t/60,GAd,'-r')
hold off
xlabel('Time (min)','FontSize',14)
ylabel('Alcoholic strength (%v/v)','FontSize',14)
set(gca,'FontSize',11);
legend('accumulated in samples collected','accumulated in one sample')
subplot(1,3,2)
plot(t/60,TC-273.15,'-k')
xlabel('Time (min)','FontSize',14);
ylabel('Head temperature (°C)','FontSize',14)
set(gca,'FontSize',11);
subplot(1,3,3)
plot(t/60,x(:,3),'-k')
xlabel('Time (min)','FontSize',14);
ylabel('Distillate (mL)','FontSize',14)
set(gca,'FontSize',11);
elseif flag_cut == 2
% ===== FIGURE 3 =====
```

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```

subplot(1,2,1)
stairs(time_process,Qcal_process,'-.k','LineWidth',1.5)
hold on
plot([time_head(end)/60 time_head(end)/60],[250 450],'--r','LineWidth',2.0)
hold off
xlabel('Time (min)','FontSize',16)
ylabel('Heating power (W)','FontSize',16)
set(gca,'FontSize',14,'YTick',linspace(250,450,3));
xlim([0 time_process(end)])
ylim([250 450])
subplot(1,2,2)
[hAx,hLine1,hLine2]=plotyy(time_process,TC,time_process,GAi);
hAx(1).YColor = 'k';
hAx(2).YColor = 'k';
ylabel(hAx(1),'Head temperature (°C)','FontSize',16) % left y-axis
ylabel(hAx(2),'Alcoholic strength (%v/v)','FontSize',16) % right y-axis
hLine1.LineStyle = '-';
hLine2.LineStyle = ':';
line(time_process,TC,'Parent',hAx(1),'LineWidth',1.5,'LineStyle', ...
      '-','Color','k','Marker','none')
line(time_process,GAi,'Parent',hAx(2),'LineWidth',2.0,'LineStyle', ...
      ':' ,'Color','k','Marker','none')
xlabel('Time (min)','FontSize',16)
hold on
plot([time_head(end)/60 time_head(end)/60],[88 100],'--r','LineWidth',2.0)
hold off
set(hAx(1),'Xlim',[0 time_process(end)]);
set(hAx(1),'Ylim',[88 100]);
set(hAx(1),'FontSize',14)
set(hAx(2),'Xlim',[0 time_process(end)]);
set(hAx(2),'Ylim',[0 75]);
set(hAx(2),'FontSize',14)
set(hAx(1),'YTick',linspace(88,100,4));
set(hAx(2),'YTick',linspace(0,75,4));
end
%=====
function [t,x,TB,TC,F,GAi,GAd,GAd_frac,rec,V,C_cong,C_cong_frac, ...
         C_rcong,C_rcong_frac,rec_cong] = alembic_outputs ...
         (Ncong,congener_PM,x0,x0_wine,u,p,odeoptions,flag_UA,flag_cut, ...
         V_head,V_heart,cut)
% This function solve the model by numeric integration and give the all the
% results. The ODE function can be excute by two configurations;
% Normal integration with ODE function (wihout ODE event). flag_cut = 1
% Integration with ODE event to make the head and heart cuts. flag_cut = 2
% Then, it is call @congener_conc function to calculate the concentrations
% of all components; alcoholic strength (GAd) and congeneres (C_cong or C_rcong).

```

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```
% In addition, @online_outputs function obtaining the boiler (TB) and
% head temperatures (TC),distillate flow (F) rate and instantaneous
% alcoholic strenght (GAi).
% Inputs:
% Ncong: number of congeners
% congener_PM: congeners molar weigth
% x0: initial concentration in head or head fraction
% x0_wine: initial concentration in wine
% u: input vector
% p: parameters vector [UAb UAc]
% odeoptions: options for odefunction
% flag_UA: UA parameter configuration
% flag_cut: ODE configuration with (2) or without (1) ode event.
% V_head: volume head
% V_heart: volume heart
% cut: string with the words 'head' or 'heart' to define the distillation
% fraction in the simulation. This option is on when flag_cut is 2
% (integration with ODE event).
% Outputs:
% t:          Integrate time vector (s)
% x:          Integrated vector from ODE function
% TB:        Boiler Temperature (K)
% TC:        Head Temperature (K)
% F:         Distillate flow rate (mL/min)
% GAi:       Instantaneous alcoholic strength (%v/v)
% GAd:       Alcoholic strength accumulated (%v/v)
% GAd_frac   Alcoholic strength in the samples collected
% rec:       Ethanol recovery (%)
% V:         Distillate volume (mL)
% C_cong:    Absolute congener concentration (mg/L)
% C_cong_frac: Absolute congener concentration in the samples collected
% C_rcong:   Relative congener concentration (g/hL.a.a.)
% C_rcong_frac: Relative congener concentration in the samples collected
% rec_cong:  Congener recovy (%)
% Ouputs

% inputs variable declaration
tspan = u(:,1);
Qcal  = u(:,2);
Tamb  = u(:,3);
% ===== selection of ODE event according the head or heart simulation ===
if strcmp(cut,'head')
    % ODE event to stop the simulation in head cut
    odeoptions.Events = @volume_head;
elseif strcmp(cut,'heart')
    % ODE event to stop the simulation in heart cut
```

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```

odeoptions.Events = @volume_heart;
elseif strcmp(cut,'none')
end
% ===== Normal integration with ODE function =====
if flag_cut == 1
    [t,x]=ode15s(@alembic_model,tspan,x0,odeoptions,u,p,flag_UA,Ncong,V_head,V_heart);
% ===== Integration with ODE event to make the head and heart cuts=====
elseif flag_cut == 2

[t,x,TE,YE,IE]=ode15s(@alembic_model,tspan,x0,odeoptions,u,p,flag_UA,Ncong,V_head,V_heart);
end
% calculations of alcoholic strength and congeners concentration
[GAd, rec,C_cong,C_rcong,rec_cong,GAd_frac,C_cong_frac,C_rcong_frac] ...
    = congener_conc(x,x0_wine,congener_PM,Ncong);
xB = x(:,2); % xB declaration
V=x(:,3); % distillate volume declaration
% Obtaining of variables TB, TC, GAi, F
[TB, TC, GAi, F] = online_outputs(xB,u,p,flag_UA);
%=====
function dxdt = alembic_model(t,x,u,p,flag_UA,Ncong,V_head,V_heart)

% This function correspond to Charentais alembic model for ethanol-water
% mixture plus congeners
% Inputs:
% t: Integration time
% x: State variables (4 for ethanol-water + 2 per congener)
% u: Input vector
% p: parameters vector p = [UAb UAc]
% Outputs:
% dxdt: state variables integrated

% state variables declaration
Mb=x(1); % Molar hold-up in bottom (mol)
xB=x(2); % Ethanol molar fraction in bottom (mol/mol)
Vd=x(3); % Distillate volume (mL)
Et_d=x(4); % Ethanol moles in distillate (mol)
xB_cong=x(4+1:4+Ncong); % Congeners molar fraction in bottom (mol/mol)
Md_cong=x(4+Ncong+1:end); % Congeners moles in distillate (mol)
% inputs variable declaration
tspan = u(:,1); % integration time
Qcal_t = u(:,2); % heating power (W)
Tamb_t = u(:,3); % room temperature (K)
% ==== execute each heating power element in their correspond time step ===
e=1;
cond=true;
while cond

```

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```

    if (t >= tspan(e)) && (t <= tspan(e+1))
        cond = false;
        Qcal = Qcal_t(e);
        Tamb = Tamb_t(e);
    else
        cond=true;
        e=1+e;
    end
end
% ===== linear fuction of heating power =====
if flag_UA == 1;
    % Global coefficient and area of heat transfer:
    % Boiler zone
    UAb = ((0.711-0.821)/(450-250))*(Qcal-250)+0.821;
    % head of alembic zone
    UAc = ((1.730-1.277)/(450-250))*(Qcal-250)+1.277;
% ===== linear function + 2*sigma (95% confidence interval) =====
elseif flag_UA == 2;
    % Boiler zone
    UAb = (((0.711-0.821)/(450-250))*(Qcal-250)+0.821)+2*0.098;
    % head of alembic zone
    UAc = (((1.730-1.277)/(450-250))*(Qcal-250)+1.277)+2*0.167;
% ===== linear function - 2*sigma (95% confidence interval) =====
elseif flag_UA == 3;
    % Boiler zone
    UAb = (((0.711-0.821)/(450-250))*(Qcal-250)+0.821)-2*0.098;
    % head of alembic zone
    UAc = (((1.730-1.277)/(450-250))*(Qcal-250)+1.277)-2*0.167;
% ===== constant parameters =====
elseif flag_UA == 4;
    % Boiler zone
    UAb = p(1);
    % head of alembic zone
    UAc = p(2);
end
% ===== THERMODYNAMIC EQUILIBRIUM ETHANOL-WATER IN THE BOILER =====
% All calculations of equilibrium are through empirical correlations
% from Sacher et al. (2013). These equations are polynomic functions
% that depend on the ethanol molar fraction (xB,xL).

% Ethanol molar fraction in the vapor flow from the bottom
yb = -59.6868501+-89.4037240*xB+-39.8552042*xB.^1.5...      % (Eq. A.9)
    +81.47664393*exp(xB)-21.7897938*exp(-xB);
% Boiler temperature
if xB <=0.1661                                             % (Eq. A.10)
    Tb=273.15+(-0.02214517+-0.05785120*xB.^1.5+0.032146591*exp(xB)).^-1;

```

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```

else
    Tb =273.15+278.3854921+-141.465178*xB+49.67113604.*xB.*log(xB)...
        +9.159930587*xB.^3+-184.225674*exp(-xB);
end
% Molar specific enthalpy in the bottom
hb = (55.678*xB+75.425)*Tb-15208.44*xB-20602.34;
% Molar specific enthalpy in the vapor flow
Hb = 36172.03-2919.83*yb+(31.461-11.976*yb)*Tb...
    +(4.063*10^-4+0.0734*yb)*Tb^2;
% Partial derivative delta(hb)/delta(xb)=f(Tb(xb))
deltahbdeltaxb = 55.678*Tb-15208.44;
% Partial derivative delta(hb)/delta(Tb)=f(xb)
deltahbdeltaTb = 55.678*xB+75.425;
% Temperature derivate respecto to ethanol concentration (xB)
if xB<=0.1661
    dTbdxB=- (1.5*-0.05785120*xB.^0.5+0.032146591*exp(xB))./ ...
        (-0.02214517+-0.05785120*xB.^1.5+0.032146591*exp(xB)).^2;
else
    dTbdxB=-141.465178+49.67113604.*log(xB)+49.67113604+ ...
        3*9.159930587*xB.^2+184.225674*exp(-xB);
end
% total derivate dhb/dxb
dhbdxb=deltahbdeltaxb+deltahbdeltaTb*dTbdxB;
% ===== IMPLICIT EQUATION - ENEGERY BALANCE IN THE BOTTOM (Eq.A.23) =====
xLstart=1.1*xB; % initial iteration value of xL
par=[xB Qcal UAb UAc Tamb yb hb Hb dhbdxb];
options=optimset('Display','off');
% solve implicit equation with fsolve to calculate xL
[xL,fval,exitflag]=fsolve(@(x) xLsolve(x,par),xLstart,options);
% ===== THERMODYNAMIC EQUILIBRIUM ETHANOL-WATER IN THE HEAD ZONE =====
% Empirical correlations are evaluate in xL
% Head temperature
if xL <=0.1661 %TL=f(xL) (K)
    TL=273.15+(-0.02214517+-0.05785120*xL.^1.5+0.032146591*exp(xL)).^-1;
else
    TL =273.15+278.3854921+-141.465178*xL+49.67113604.*xL.*log(xL)...
        +9.159930587*xL.^3+-184.225674*exp(-xL);
end
% Ethanol molar fraction in the distillate flow
yd = -59.6868501+-89.4037240*xL+-39.8552042*xL.^1.5...
    +81.47664393*exp(xL)-21.7897938*exp(-xL);
% Molar specific enthalpy in the liquid reflux
hL = (55.678*xL+75.425)*TL-15208.44*xL-20602.34;
% Molar specific enthalpy in the distillate flow
Hd = 36172.03-2919.83*yd+(31.461-11.976*yd)*TL...
    +(4.063*10^-4+0.0734*yd)*TL^2;

```

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```

% ===== Mass balances in the head (partial condenser) =====
% Vapor flow from the bottom
Vb= UAc*(TL-Tamb) / ( (Hb-Hd)+(yb-yd)/(xL-yd)*(Hd-hL) );
% Liquid natural reflux flow
L =-UAc*(TL-Tamb) / ( (hL-Hd)+(xL-yd)/(yb-yd)*(Hd-Hb) );
% Distillate flow
Vd = Vb-L;
% ===== EMPIRICAL CORRELACIÓN DENSITY (NEURBURG 1994) =====
MW1=46.07;           % Weight molar Etanol
MW2=18.0153;        % Weigth molar water
MWp=MW1*yd+(1-yd)*MW2; % Weigth molar mixture
rhow=1;             % g/mL density water pure
% apparent molal volume of liquid mixtures [m3/kmol] (Eq. A.16)
phi=5.1214e-2+...
    6.549e-3*yd+7.406e-5*(TL-273.15);
% Mixture density (Eq. A.16)
rhop=MWp/(phi*1000*yd+(1-yd)*(MW2/rhow));
% Distillate flow rate (mL/s)
F=Vd*MWp*(1/rhop);
% ===== ODES ETHANOL-WATER =====
dxdt=zeros(6,1);
% Total mass balance in the boiler
dxdt(1) = L-Vb;
% Ethanol mass balance in the boiler
dxdt(2) = 1/Mb*(L*(xL-xB)-Vb*(yb-xB));
% Toal mass balances in the distillate (distillate volume)
dxdt(3) = F;
% Ethanol mas balance in the distillate (ethanol moles)
dxdt(4) = Vd*yd;
% ===== CONGENER CALCULATIONS =====
Kcong_b   = zeros(Ncong,1);
Kcong_c   = zeros(Ncong,1);
yb_cong   = zeros(Ncong,1);
xL_cong   = zeros(Ncong,1);
yd_cong   = zeros(Ncong,1);

for i=1:Ncong
% parameters polynomial approximation for each congener (eq A.9)
PolKcong = zeros(Ncong,7);
% Acetaldehyde
PolKcong(1,1:7)=[2132.48647470687 -7325.32158274884 9975.65026598049 ...
    -6877.34768142094 2557.05908782731 -514.677851684226 59.8488158884235];
% Methanol
PolKcong(2,1:7)=[344.843341522534 -1174.41754890585 1583.17398976036 ...
    -1073.73582253337 388.389261160545 -73.6515297026980 7.47712492793083];
% Ethyl acetate

```

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```

PolKcong(3,1:7)=[6708.80545814955 -22825.1298638850 30638.8774877421 ...
    -20622.5403332238 7323.26442993318 -1326.16274539085 108.370963453395];
% Linalool
PolKcong(4,1:7)=[5903.54406919218 -19642.5313045736 25537.6690914762 ...
    -16362.2715807274 5343.77291171908 -823.424096778676 45.8635924063960];
% Hexanoic acid
PolKcong(5,1:7)=[79.3503646604582 -265.323418070129 347.411506679424 ...
    -225.065622269698 74.9248170603414 -11.9950927956312 0.736427102093912];
% Phenethyl alcohol
PolKcong(6,1:7)=[349.984114473148 -1168.19810837707 1525.76323298408 ...
    -984.481408366268 325.376073822477 -51.3026635899384 3.01613099316598];
% Partition coefficient in bottom
Kcong_b(i,1)=PolKcong(i,1)*xB^6+PolKcong(i,2)*xB^5+PolKcong(i,3)*xB^4+ ...
    PolKcong(i,4)*xB^3+PolKcong(i,5)*xB^2+PolKcong(i,6)*xB^1+PolKcong(i,7);
% Partition coefficient in head
Kcong_c(i,1)=PolKcong(i,1)*xL^6+PolKcong(i,2)*xL^5+PolKcong(i,3)*xL^4+ ...
    PolKcong(i,4)*xL^3+PolKcong(i,5)*xL^2+PolKcong(i,6)*xB^1+PolKcong(i,7);
% Thermodynamic equilibrium L-V relationships of congeners in bottom
yb_cong(i,1)=Kcong_b(i,1).*xB_cong(i);
% Congener molar fraction in the liquid reflux
xL_cong(i,1)=(Vb*yb_cong(i,1))./(L+Vd*Kcong_c(i,1));
% Thermodynamic equilibrium L-V relationship of congeners in head
yd_cong(i,1)=xL_cong(i,1).*Kcong_c(i,1);
% ===== ODES CONGENERS =====
% Congener component balance in the boiler
dxdt(4+i)= 1/Mb*(L*(xL_cong(i,1)-xB_cong(i))-Vb*(yb_cong(i,1)-xB_cong(i)));
% Congener component balance in the distillate
dxdt(4+Ncong+i)= Vd*yd_cong(i);
end
%=====
function [value,isterminal,direction] = ...
    volume_head(t,x,u,p,flag_UA,Ncong,V_head,V_heart)
% This function correspond to ODE event. The function determine the time
% to stop the simulation when comply a specific event.
% The event is stop the simulation when the distillate volume of simulation
% is equal to head volume.
value = x(3)-V_head;
isterminal = 1;
direction = 0;
%=====
function [value,isterminal,direction] = ...
    volume_heart(t,x,u,p,flag_UA,Ncong,V_head,V_heart)
% This function correspond to ODE event. The function determine the time
% to stop the simulation when comply a specific event.
% The event is stop the simulation when the distillate volume of simulation
% is equal to heart volume.

```

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```

value = x(3)-V_heart;
isterminal = 1;
direction = 0;
=====
function [GAd,rec,C_cong,C_rcong,rec_cong,GAd_frac,C_cong_frac, ...
    C_rcong_frac] = congener_conc(x,x0_wine,MW,Ncong)
% This function calculate the alcoholic strength, ethanol recovery,
% absolute congener concentration, relative congener concentration
% accumulated in the distillate. In addition, are calculate the alcoholic
% strength, absolute and relative congener concentration where were
% collected the samples or fractions, i.e, the accumulated in the each step
% of integration time.
% Inputs
% x:          Integrated vector from ODE function
% x0_wine:    Initial concentrations in wine
% MW:        congeners molar weigth (g/mol)
% Ncong:     Number of congeners
% Ouputs
% GAd:       Alcoholic strength accumulated (%v/v)
% rec:       Ethanol recovery (%)
% C_cong:    Absolute congener concentration (mg/L)
% C_rcong:   Relative congener concentration (g/hL.a.a.)
% rec_cong:  Congener recoveries (%)
% GAd_frac:  Alcoholic strength in the samples collected
% C_cong_frac: Absolute congener concentration in the samples collected
% C_rcong_frac: Relative congener concentration in the samples collected

% Variables declaration
Mb      = x(:,1);           % Molar hold-up in bottom (mol)
xb      = x(:,2);           % Ethanol molar fraction in bottom (mol/mol)
V       = x(:,3);           % Distillate volume (mL)
Md      = x(:,4);           % Ethanol moles in distillate (mol)
xb_cong = x(:,4+1:4+Ncong); % Congeners molar fraction in bottom (mol/mol)
Md_cong = x(:,4+Ncong+1:end); % Congeners moles in distillate (mol)
Mb_wine = x0_wine(1);      % Initial moles in bottom
xb_wine = x0_wine(2);      % Initial ethanol molar fration in bottom
xb_cong_wine = x0_wine(4+1:4+Ncong); % Initial congeners molar fraction in bottom
GAd = Md.*46.07.*(1/0.7893).*100./V; % Alcoholic strenght (%v/v)
rec = (Md*100)./(Mb_wine*xb_wine); % Ethanol recovery (%)
[nrow,ncolumn] = size(Md_cong); % variables dimension
C_cong      = zeros(nrow,ncolumn); % Absolute congeners concentration (mg/L)
C_rcong     = zeros(nrow,ncolumn); % Relative congeners concentration (g/hL.a.a.)
rec_cong    = zeros(nrow,ncolumn); % Congener recoveries (%)
GAd_frac    = zeros(nrow-1,1);     % Alcoholic strength in the samples
C_cong_frac = zeros(nrow-1,ncolumn); % Absolute congener concentration in the samples
C_rcong_frac = zeros(nrow-1,ncolumn); % Relative congener concentration in the samples

```

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```

for j=2:length(Md)
    GAd_frac(j-1)    = (Md(j)-Md(j-1))*46.07*(1/0.7893)*100/(V(j)-V(j-1));
    for i=1:ncolumn
        C_cong(:,i)  = (Md_cong(:,i)*MW(i)*1000)./(V/1000);
        C_rcong(:,i) = (Md_cong(:,i)*MW(i)*1000*100)./(V.*(GAd/100));
        rec_cong(:,i) = (Md_cong(:,i)*100)./(Mb_wine*xb_cong_wine(i));
        C_cong_frac(j-1,i) = ((Md_cong(j,i)-Md_cong(j-1,i))*MW(i)*1000)./ ...
            ((V(j)-V(j-1))/1000);
        C_rcong_frac(j-1,i) = ((Md_cong(j,i)-Md_cong(j-1,i))*MW(i)*1000*100)./ ...
            ((V(j)-V(j-1)).*(GAd_frac(j-1)/100));
    end
end

%=====
function [Tb TL yd F]=evalfun(xB,u,p,flag_UA)
% This function eval the xB integrated obtained from Ode function.
% The aim is obtaining the temperatures data, instantaneous ethanol moles
% in the distillate and distillate flow rate.
% Inputs:
% xB:          Integrated vector of xB (x(:,2))
% u:           Input vector
% p:           Parameter vector p = [UAb UAc]
% Outputs:
% Tb:          Boiler temperature (K).
% TL:          Head temperature (K).
% yd:          Ethanol molar fration in the vapor that become in distillate

% Input variales declaration
tspan = u(1); % Time
Qcal  = u(2); % Heatig power
Tamb  = u(3); % Room temperature
% ===== linear fuction of heating power =====
if flag_UA == 1;
    % Global coefficient and area of heat transfer:
    % Boiler zone
    UAb = ((0.711-0.821)/(450-250))*(Qcal-250)+0.821;
    % head of alembic zone
    UAc = ((1.730-1.277)/(450-250))*(Qcal-250)+1.277;
% ===== linear function + 2*sigma (95% confidence interval) =====
elseif flag_UA == 2;
    % Boiler zone
    UAb = (((0.711-0.821)/(450-250))*(Qcal-250)+0.821)+2*0.098;
    % head of alembic zone
    UAc = (((1.730-1.277)/(450-250))*(Qcal-250)+1.277)+2*0.167;
% ===== linear function - 2*sigma (95% confidence interval) =====
elseif flag_UA == 3;

```

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```

% Boiler zone
UAb = (((0.711-0.821)/(450-250))*(Qcal-250)+0.821)-2*0.098;
% head of alembic zone
UAc = (((1.730-1.277)/(450-250))*(Qcal-250)+1.277)-2*0.167;
% ===== constant parameters =====
elseif flag_UA == 4;
    % Boiler zone
    UAb = p(1);
    % head of alembic zone
    UAc = p(2);
end
% ===== THERMODYNAMIC EQUILIBRIUM ETHANOL-WATER IN THE BOILER =====
% All calculations of equilibrium are through empirical correlations
% from Sacher et al. (2013). These equations are polynomic functions
% that depend on the ethanol molar fraction (xB,xL).

% Ethanol molar fraction in the vapor flow from the bottom
yb = -59.6868501+-89.4037240*xB+-39.8552042*xB.^1.5...      % (Eq. A.9)
    +81.47664393*exp(xB)-21.7897938*exp(-xB);
% Boiler temperature
if xB <=0.1661                                             % (Eq. A.10)
    Tb=273.15+(-0.02214517+-0.05785120*xB.^1.5+0.032146591*exp(xB)).^-1;
else
    Tb =273.15+278.3854921+-141.465178*xB+49.67113604.*xB.*log(xB)...
        +9.159930587*xB.^3+-184.225674*exp(-xB);
end
% Molar specific enthalpy in the bottom
hb = (55.678*xB+75.425)*Tb-15208.44*xB-20602.34;
% Molar specific enthalpy in the vapor flow
Hb = 36172.03-2919.83*yb+(31.461-11.976*yb)*Tb...
    +(4.063*10^-4+0.0734*yb)*Tb^2;
% Partial derivative delta(hb)/delta(xb)=f(Tb(xb))
deltahbdeltaxb = 55.678*Tb-15208.44;
% Partial derivative delta(hb)delta(Tb)=f(xb)
deltahbdeltaTb = 55.678*xB+75.425;
% Temperature derivate respecto to ethanol concentration (xB)
if xB<=0.1661
    dTbdxB=- (1.5*-0.05785120*xB.^0.5+0.032146591*exp(xB))./ ...
        (-0.02214517+-0.05785120*xB.^1.5+0.032146591*exp(xB)).^2;
else
    dTbdxB=-141.465178+49.67113604.*log(xB)+49.67113604+ ...
        3*9.159930587*xB.^2+184.225674*exp(-xB);
end
% total derivate dhb/dxb
dhdxb=deltahbdeltaxb+deltahbdeltaTb*dTbdxB;
% ===== IMPLICIT EQUATION - ENEGERY BALANCE IN THE BOTTOM (Eq.A.23) =====

```

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```

xLstart=1.1*xB; % initial iteration value of xL
par=[xB Qcal UAb UAc Tamb yb hb Hb dhbdxb];
options=optimset('Display','off');
% solve implicit equation with fsolve to calculate xL
[xL,fval,exitflag]=fsolve(@(x) xLsolve(x,par),xLstart,options);
% ===== THERMODYNAMIC EQUILIBRIUM ETHANOL-WATER IN THE HEAD ZONE =====
% Empirical correlations are evaluate in xL
% Head temperature
if xL <=0.1661 %TL=f(xL) (K)
    TL=273.15+(-0.02214517+-0.05785120*xL.^1.5+0.032146591*exp(xL)).^-1;
else
    TL =273.15+278.3854921+-141.465178*xL+49.67113604.*xL.*log(xL)...
        +9.159930587*xL.^3+-184.225674*exp(-xL);
end
% Ethanol molar fraction in the distillate flow
yd = -59.6868501+-89.4037240*xL+-39.8552042*xL.^1.5...
    +81.47664393*exp(xL)-21.7897938*exp(-xL);
% Molar specific enthalpy in the liquid reflux
hL = (55.678*xL+75.425)*TL-15208.44*xL-20602.34;
% Molar specific enthalpy in the distillate flow
Hd = 36172.03-2919.83*yd+(31.461-11.976*yd)*TL...
    +(4.063*10^-4+0.0734*yd)*TL^2;
% ===== Mass balances in the head (partial condenser) =====
% Vapor flow from the bottom
Vb= UAc*(TL-Tamb) / ( (Hb-Hd)+(yb-yd)/(xL-yd)*(Hd-hL) );
% Liquid natural reflux flow
L =-UAc*(TL-Tamb) / ( (hL-Hd)+(xL-yd)/(yb-yd)*(Hd-Hb) );
% Distillate flow
Vd = Vb-L;
% ===== EMPIRICAL CORRELACIÓN DENSITY (NEURBURG 1994) =====
MW1=46.07; % Weight molar Etanol
MW2=18.0153; % Weight molar water
MWp=MW1*yd+(1-yd)*MW2; % Weight molar mixture
rhow=1; % g/mL density water pure
% apparent molal volume of liquid mixtures [m3/kmol] (Eq. A.16)
phi=5.1214e-2+...
    6.549e-3*yd+7.406e-5*(TL-273.15);
% Mixture density (Eq. A.16)
rhop=MWp/(phi*1000*yd+(1-yd)*(MW2/rhow));
% Distillate flow rate (mL/s)
F=Vd*MWp*(1/rhop);
%=====
function [TB, TC, GAi, F] = online_outputs(xB,u,p,flag_UA)
% This function concatenate the equilibrium temperatures, instantaneous
% alcoholic strength and distillate flow rate. This variables correspond
% to on-line measures variables in the experiments.

```

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```

% inputs:
% xB:          Integrated vector of xB (x(:,2))
% u:          Input vector
% p:          Parameter vector p = [UAb UAc]
% flag_UA:    UA parameter configuration
% outputs:
% TB:         Boiler temperature (K).
% TC:         Head temperature (K).
% GAi:        Instantaneous alcoholic strength
% F:          Distillate flow rate (mL/min)

% Input variables declaration
tspan = u(:,1);
Qcal  = u(:,2);
Tamb  = u(:,3);
% vector creation
TB = zeros(length(xB),1); % Boiler temperature (K)
TC = zeros(length(xB),1); % Head temperature (K)
yD = zeros(length(xB),1); % Ethanol molar fraction in the vapor (mol/mol)
F   = zeros(length(xB),1); % Distillate flow rate (mL/s)
% ===== EVALUATION OF EVALFUN FOR EACH ELEMENT OF xB =====
for i=1:length(xB)
    xb=xB(i);
    ui = [tspan(i) Qcal(i) Tamb(i)];
    [Tb, TL, yd, f] = evalfun(xb,ui,p,flag_UA);
    TB(i) = Tb;
    TC(i) = TL;
    yD(i) = yd;
    F(i)  = f*60; % here, distillate flow rate is multiplicate for 60 to obtain mL/min
end
% This polynomial function relationship the head temperature equilibrium
% with the alcoholic strength of distillate.
P=[-38.950116015168470 2.310609445800233e+02 -5.482530421230588e+02 ...
    7.048795688586179e+02 -5.700321285089950e+02 3.213122048471700e+02 ...
    0.001131244289002];
GAi = polyval(P,yD); % instantaneous alcoholic strength
%=====
function f=xLsolve(xL,par)
% This function contains the routine that calculate xL by nonlinear equation
% solver (fsolve).
% Inputs:
% xL: variable of iteration with fsolve
% par: vector parameters that contain variables that are calculate previous
% to enter to this function.
% Outputs:
% f: correspond to value of implicit equation (A.23)

```

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Model code

```

% Variable declaration
xB      = par(1);
Qcal    = par(2);
UAb     = par(3);
UAc     = par(4);
Tamb    = par(5);
yb      = par(6);
hb      = par(7);
Hb      = par(8);
dhbdxB = par(9);
% Boiler temperature
if xB <= 0.1661
    Tb = 273.15 + (-0.02214517 + -0.05785120 * xB.^1.5 + 0.032146591 * exp(xB)).^-1;
else
    Tb = 273.15 + 278.3854921 + -141.465178 * xB + 49.67113604 * xB .* log(xB) ...
        + 9.159930587 * xB.^3 + -184.225674 * exp(-xB);
end
% Head temperature
if xL <= 0.1661
    TL = 273.15 + (-0.02214517 + -0.05785120 * xL.^1.5 + 0.032146591 * exp(xL)).^-1;
else
    TL = 273.15 + 278.3854921 + -141.465178 * xL + 49.67113604 * xL .* log(xL) ...
        + 9.159930587 * xL.^3 + -184.225674 * exp(-xL);
end
% Ethanol molar fraction in the distillate flow
yd = -59.6868501 + -89.4037240 * xL + -39.8552042 * xL.^1.5 ...
    + 81.47664393 * exp(xL) - 21.7897938 * exp(-xL);
% Molar specific enthalpy in the liquid reflux
hL = (55.678 * xL + 75.425) * TL - 15208.44 * xL - 20602.34;
% Molar specific enthalpy in the distillate flow
Hd = 36172.03 - 2919.83 * yd + (31.461 - 11.976 * yd) * TL ...
    + (4.063 * 10^-4 + 0.0734 * yd) * TL^2;
% Vapor flow from the bottom
Vb = UAc * (TL - Tamb) / ((Hb - Hd) + (yb - yd) / (xL - yd) * (Hd - hL));
% Liquid natural reflux flow
L = -UAc * (TL - Tamb) / ((hL - Hd) + (xL - yd) / (yb - yd) * (Hd - Hb));
% Implicit equation that depend on xL, F(xL)=0.
f = -(L * (xL - xB) - Vb * (yb - xB)) * (dhbdxB) + L * (hL - hb) - Vb * (Hb - hb) + (Qcal - UAb * (Tb - Tamb));

```